

Guidelines & recommendations for regulation and policy instruments

Deliverable 5.6

Guidelines & recommendations for regulation and policy instruments

D5.6: Guidelines & recommendations for regulation and policy instruments
Deliverable 5.6

Summary

Within the scope of WP5 – Society, governance, policy, the aim of this deliverable D5.6 is to provide guidelines and recommendations for future policy and regulation instruments, according to the reality of each of the six Living Labs of B-WaterSmart: Alicante (Spain), Bodø (Norway), East Frisia (Germany), Flanders (Belgium), Lisbon (Portugal) and Venice (Italy).

Based on the expertise of the deployment of strategies, instruments and solutions in the six Living Labs of B-WaterSmart project, this document describes the following aspects:

- (i) the role of the policy and regulation **instruments** to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society;
- (ii) the **scope** of the policy recommendations, according to the topics addressed by the project Living Labs, namely – **Digitalisation & IoT, Drinking water supply, Energy, Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others, Water reuse, and Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses**;
- (iii) the **approach** followed to produce the recommendations, based on the work developed in the six living labs, contributions from other project activities (within WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6), and two dedicated sessions on policy and regulation;
- (iv) the **mapping** of current policy and regulation instruments addressing water-related circularity at European, national, and LL levels;
- (v) a **critical analysis of the major P&R issues** for achieving water-related circularity, and
- (vi) **recommendations for policy and regulation** for water-smart systems, related to the six above-mentioned topics.

The proposed policy recommendations to foster the implementation circular water solutions in Europe are expected to be applicable to each of the EU Member-States (MSs). They supported the production of a set of four policy briefs from this project, targeted to improve policy and regulation frameworks at local, national and the EU levels, on energy, water reuse, nutrients recovery, and stormwater for agriculture use. The policy briefs are the subject of the project deliverable [D5.8](#).

Deliverable number	Work package
D5.6	WP5
Lead beneficiary	Deliverable author(s)
LNEC – National Laboratory of Civil Engineering	Maria Adriana Cardoso, Maria João Rosa, Rita Ribeiro (LNEC) Arvid van Dam, Raül Glotzbach (KWR)

- All the participants of the dedicated session on Policy and Regulation for water reuse, carried out by the Lisbon LL on the 12th January 2024.

Date	History of Changes
Oct 2024	Version reviewed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table of contents was updated. • In section 2.2, examples were included to better demonstrate how the current policies and regulations will accelerate the transition towards CE. The fifth paragraph was extended, the last paragraph was changed, and three new paragraphs were included to add these examples. • Section 2.3 was moved to section 5.2, as its introduction in a new subsection, to make the contents on business models (BMs) clearer, namely, to better explain the BM definition and why it is important in the context of regulation and policy instruments, the link between circular BMs and policy/regulation, and better highlight the link between business models and the concept of living labs. • References were added. • List of references was updated.
Oct 2024	Version reviewed after Brussels' meeting – following comments from Violeta Kuzmickaite: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table of contents was updated. • Executive summary was changed and complemented, so it can provide an autonomous document facilitating dissemination and communication with policy-makers at EU level. Links to the sections in the document and to the policy briefs were introduced, examples were added to better address and link to the contribution of the work developed in B-WaterSmart. • Sections 4.3.1, 5.1.2, 5.1.4, 5.2.1, 5.2.2 were updated including the highlights suggested. • Section 5.2.3 title was updated. • Chapter 7 was updated in accordance to the changes in the executive summary. • References were added. • List of references was updated.
Feb 2025	Version reviewed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table of contents was updated. • Section 2.2 was shortened and reorganised, and more examples were included to better demonstrate how the current policies and regulations will accelerate the transition towards CE. • Section 5.2.1 (that incorporated the original section 2.3 in the last review) was expanded to better highlight the link between circular business models (CBM) and the concept of living labs, to better explain the CBM definition and why it is important in the context of regulation and policy instruments, and the link between CBMs and policy/regulation, also in relation to D4.4. • References were added and the list of references was updated.

Table of contents

Author Contributions	II
Acknowledgments	II
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	VIII
Executive summary	1
1 Introduction	6
1.1. Objectives and scope.....	6
1.2. Structure	6
2 Role of policy and regulation instruments to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society	8
2.1 Overview of key challenges in the transition to a water-smarter society	8
2.2 Role of policy and regulation instruments to accelerate the transition	10
3 Water-related resources addressed in B-WaterSmart	14
4 Approach	15
4.1 Overview	15
4.2 Contributions from B-WaterSmart developments	16
4.2.1 Contributions from WP4, WP5 and WP6.....	16
4.2.2 Contributions from WP1 InAll partners strategic planning	17
4.3 Interactive session on Policy & Regulation.....	17
4.3.1 General overview	17
4.3.2 Working tables organization	18
4.3.3 Ranking of topics	19
4.4 Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation focused on water reuse and related-issues ..	19
5 Policy and regulation instruments on water-related circularity addressed in B-WaterSmart	20
5.1 Overview of EU instruments	20
5.1.1 General	20
5.1.2 Regulatory and legal barriers for the water reuse in agriculture for irrigation	21
5.1.3 European legislation and directives on stormwater and brown water reuse in agriculture	22
5.1.4 Next Steps: Towards Direct Potable Water Reuse?	23
5.2 Circular business model innovation and policy and regulation.....	24
5.2.1 General aspects, impact of regulation on circular business model innovation	24
5.2.2 LL orientation towards policies and regulations	26
5.2.3 Circular Business Models Innovation stages and dependence on policies and regulations	27

5.3	Mapping policy and regulation instruments, issues and strengths at EU and LL level ...	30
5.3.1	Digitalisation and IoT	31
5.3.2	Drinking water	32
5.3.3	Energy	34
5.3.4	Nutrients, biosolids and others	36
5.3.5	Reclaimed water	37
5.3.6	Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.....	44
6	Analysis of major water-related issues	47
6.1	Common issues	47
6.1.1	Digitalisation and IoT on water	47
6.1.2	Drinking water supply	47
6.1.3	Energy	47
6.1.4	Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others	47
6.1.5	Water reuse	48
6.1.6	Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.....	49
6.2	Specific issues	49
6.2.1	Digitalisation and IoT on water	49
6.2.2	Drinking water supply	49
6.2.3	Energy	49
6.2.4	Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others	50
6.2.5	Water reuse	50
6.2.6	Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.....	52
7	Recommendations	53
7.1	Cross-cutting recommendations	53
7.2	Digitalisation and IoT on water	54
7.3	Drinking water supply.....	54
7.4	Energy.....	55
7.5	Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others.....	55
7.6	Water reuse	56
7.7	Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.....	59
7.8	Next step - policy briefs development.....	59
8	References	61
9	Online references	68
	Annex 1 List of B-WaterSmart tools and technologies	69
	B-WaterSmart tools and technologies	70
	Annex 2 Interactive session on policy and regulation	72
	Discussions outcomes	73
a.	Digitalisation and IoT Table 1	73

b.	Drinking water Table 2	76
c.	Nutrients, biosolids and others Table 4	79
d.	Reclaimed water Table 5	82
e.	Stormwater Table 6.....	85

Ranking of 6 topics relevance to produce the B-WaterSmart policy briefs	88
--	-----------

List of Figures

Figure 1. Approach adopted to develop the recommendations.	15
Figure 2: The InAll process 5-phased schedule program (Cardoso et al., 2022)	17
Figure 3. Overview of the European water-related policies (WISE, 2023)	20
Figure 4: Indirect and direct potable reuse.....	24
Figure 5. Feedback loop of P&R	30
Figure 6. Digitalisation and IoT Working table 1.	73
Figure 7. Drinking water Working table 2	76
Figure 8. Nutrients, biosolids and others Working table 4.....	79
Figure 9. Reclaimed water Working table 5.	82
Figure 10. Stormwater Working table 6.....	85
Figure 11. Ranking of all participants	88
Figure 12. Ranking of LLs	88

List of Tables

Table 1. Resources addressed in the B-WaterSmart LLs.....	14
Table 2. Questions proposed to guide the gathering of information.	16
Table 3. Working tables organization	18
Table 4. Set of questions for discussion Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation	19
Table 5. Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in digitalisation and IoT	31
Table 6. Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in drinking water.....	32
Table 7 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in energy	34
Table 8 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in nutrients, biosolids, and others	36
Table 9 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in water reuse	38
Table 10 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in stormwater	44
Table 11. Working table 1 outcome Digitalisation and IoT	73
Table 12. Working table 2 outcome Drinking water	76
Table 13. Working table 4 outcome Nutrients, biosolids and others	79
Table 14. Working table 5 outcome Reclaimed water.....	82
Table 15. Working table 6 outcome Stormwater	85

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

adelphi	: Adelphi research gemeinnützige
ARERA	: L'Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente
B3S	: Information Technology security standard water/wastewater
BDSG	: Federal Data Protection Act (Esta-Frisia)
BWS AF	: Water-Smartness Assessment Framework
C40 Cities	: Global network of mayors of the world's leading cities united in action to confront the climate crisis
CBM	: Circular business models
CBMI	: Circular business models innovation
CE	: Circular Economy
CEAP	: Circular Economy Action Plan
CETAQUA	: Centro Tecnológico del Agua
Cl ₂	: Chlorine
COM	: Communication
CoP	: Community of Practice
DPR	: Direct potable reuse
DWD	: Drinking Water Directive
Dx.y	: Deliverable x.y
E-coli	: Escherichia coli
EC	: European Commission
EC-ECCE	: European Commission, Energy, Climate change, Environment
EC-SP	: European Commission strategy and policy
EC-Water	: European Commission, Energy, Climate change, Environment. Topic water
ECI	: European Critical Infrastructure
EDR	: Electrodialysis reversal
EEA	: European Environment Agency

ELP	: Long-Term Decarbonization Strategy
ENISA	: European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ERSAR	: Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos (Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority)
ETC	: European Topic Centre
EU	: European Union
EurEau	: European Federation of National Water Services Associations
GDPR	: General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	: Geographic Information System
HWDP	: Rainwater and Drought Plan (Flanders)
IAM	: Infrastructure asset management
ICS-UL	: Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa
IDN	: Instituto da Defesa Nacional
InAll	: Innovation Alliance
IoT	: Internet of Things
IPR	: Indirect potable reuse
IRAR	: Instituto Regulador de Águas e Resíduos
ISO	: International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	: Information technology
IWA	: International Water Association
IWW	: IWW Rheinisch-Westfälisches Institut für Wasserforschung gGmbH
KRITIS	: Critical infrastructure
KWR	: Water Research Institute
LL	: Living Lab
LL _i	: Living Lab problem-owner
LMHV	: Food Hygiene Regulation (East Frisia)
LNEC	: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil

NAS	: National Adaptation Strategy
NIS2	: Directive (EU) 2022/2555
OECD	: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
P	: Phosphorus
PENSAARP2030:	Portuguese strategic plan for the decade, for water, wastewater, and stormwater services
PER	: Renewable Energy Plan
PERAL	: Lisbon water reuse strategic plan
PESTLE	: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental
PNA	: National Water Plan
PNIEC	: National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan
PNRR	: National Recovery and Resilience Plan
PNUEA	: National Plan for Efficient Water Use
P&R	: Policy and regulation
QMRA	: Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
RA	: Risk Assessment
R&D	: Research and development
RR	: Resource Recovery
RWO	: Rainwater Ordinance
SDG	: Sustainable Development Goal
SWOT	: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
Tech.	: Technological
Tx.y	: Task x.y
UN	: United Nations
UNED	: Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia
UWC	: Urban Water Cycle

UWOT	: Model for simulation of the urban water cycle from source-to-treatment-to-tap, supporting planning and assessment of distributed interventions
UWWTD	: Urban Wastewater Treatment
VAP	: Flemish Adaptation Plan
VITO	: VITO nv
VKP	: Flemish Climate Policy Plan
Vlakwa	: Vlaams Kenniscentrum Water
VMP	: Flemish Mitigation Plan
W-E-P	: Water-Energy-Phosphorus
WAREG	: European Association of Public Authorities
WFD	: Water Framework Directive
WISE	: Water Information System for Europe
WoLL	: Water-Oriented Living Labs
WP	: Work Package
WRRF	: Water Resource Recovery Facility
WWTP	: Wastewater treatment plant

Executive summary

Within the scope of WP5 – Society, governance, policy, the aim of this deliverable D5.6 is to provide guidelines and recommendations for future policy and regulation (P&R) instruments, based on the work developed by the **six Living Labs** of B-WaterSmart that were striving to create and implement tools, strategies, and solutions for improving water smartness in three cities and three regions in coastal Europe: Alicante (Spain), Bodø (Norway), East Frisia (Germany), Flanders (Belgium), Lisbon (Portugal), and Venice (Italy). This document includes targeted policy recommendations to create an enabling environment for a wide **application of water-smart solutions**, at local, national and EU levels, in the following six **topics: Digitalisation & IoT, Drinking water supply, Energy, Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others, Water reuse, and Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.**

This document presents:

- (i) the importance of the policy and regulation **instruments** to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society (chapter 2);
- (ii) the **scope** of the recommendations, according to the topics addressed by the project Living Labs (chapter 3);
- (iii) the **approach** followed to produce the policy recommendations, taking into account the work developed in the six Living Labs, contributions from other project activities (T1.4, deliverable D1.5; T4.4; T5.2, [D5.3](#); T6.2, [D6.3](#)), and two dedicated meetings not originally planned (T2.4, the Alicante project meeting on the six abovementioned topics, with about 70 project participants; the Lisbon LL meeting on water reuse, with 18 participants, half of which external P&R experts) (chapter 4);
- (iv) the **mapping** of current policy and regulation **instruments** (directives, laws, regulations, agendas, plans, strategies) addressing water-related circularity, main issues and strengths, at European and LL levels (chapter 5);
- (v) a **critical analysis of the major P&R issues** for achieving water-related circularity, common among the LLs as well as LL specific (chapter 6), and
- (vi) **cross-cutting and topic-specific recommendations to policy-makers** (on the six water-related topics mentioned above), for overcoming the major issues identified to implement water smartness at local, national and EU levels (chapter 7).

Examples of **major issues** shared among the six LLs and calling for P&R improvement (section 6.1) are:

- (i) the national **data protection laws** derived from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) have consequences in data confidentiality and security that hinder data collection needed for improving water-smartness, e.g. water efficiency as recently introduced by the new Drinking Water Directive (DWD);
- (ii) the need to allocate fit-for-purpose water quality to **avoid/limit using drinking water for non-potable uses**;
- (iii) the need to facilitate the management between the **water systems** and the **energy distribution grid**, in order to minimise the need for energy storage while ensuring the quality of electricity on the distribution grid;
- (iv) the lack of EU policy for promoting **climate-adaptive housing**;

- (v) the need for a consensual EU regulation concerning the **organic fertilizers** obtained from the urban wastewater treatment, including the required characteristics/standards, to promote their recovery and market acceptance, and the need to look for value prepositive markets, such as urban landscaping (currently, the market for valuing nutrients is not appellative - low revenue);
- (vi) the lack of EU agenda and strategy on **water reuse** covering all uses, non-potable and potable, indirect (including managed aquifer recharge) and direct, to monitor and increase the safety of the current indirect reuse, and to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the water-energy-waste-food nexus;
- (vii) the need for stakeholders' involvement in **rain/stormwater** management as a shared challenge with a clear definition of roles, responsibility and ownership (including who and how to pay for an unstable source as stormwater) and to promote rain/stormwater storage (preferentially using nature-based solutions to manage quantity and quality) and use in rural and urban spaces.

Examples of the **key cross-cutting P&R recommendations at EU level**, detailed in section 7.1, are:

- (i) ensure **coherence among sectors** (water, energy, waste, food, health) and **across levels** (EU, national, local) (e.g., (i) exclude biosolids/sludge from waste legislation; (ii) the targets for renewable energy production and for water-related circularities need to be coherent, namely, the hydrogen production may aggravate the local water scarcity, compromising (agricultural and industrial) food production; (iii) the energy distribution grid management must consider the water utilities as energy consumers but also as producers);
- (ii) develop **coherent EU-national-local strategic plans on water and related resources**, supported by a clear, quantitative, and objective-driven assessment, e.g. using the developed Water Smartness Assessment Framework ([D6.3](#));
- (iii) promote co-work among stakeholders (water authorities, managers, researchers and other experts) for decision-making and **periodic update of the policy and regulation instruments with the best available knowledge** for achieving the EU water-related objectives – e.g., the establishment of Water-Oriented Living Labs (WoLLs) creates very effective environments, particularly in highly regulated contexts, such as the water sector, for collaborative innovation among public authorities water companies, technological and solution providers, and research institutes, facilitating the testing and improvement of P&R instruments (as demonstrated in LLs Lisbon and Venice);
- (iv) promote **the mindset and semantics' shifting from “wastewater treatment” to “resource recovery”** and valuing the water quality rather than its ‘history’, i.e., privileging ‘water’ over ‘wastewater’, which would contribute to a generational change towards an increased market acceptance of recovered water, nutrients and biosolids. Adopt this new terminology in future EU documents and communication actions, and update the current ones accordingly.

On **digitalisation and IoT**, the key recommendations at EU level (section 7.2) are to:

- (i) promote mechanisms for the continuous update and monitoring of IT threats and solutions against unauthorized access to digital systems of water utilities and water authorities (e.g., the Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority introduced a Security and Resilience Index in the quality of service assessment);

- (ii) produce **guidelines or standards of fit-for-purpose data specification**, comprehensively demonstrating the value, both from the economic and the innovation points of view, **of the shared data**;
- (iii) clarify the **boundaries between confidential and open data**, promoting the safe availability of sound anonymous shared data, and to transpose the above to national and/or regional levels, when and if applicable.

On **drinking water**, recommendations at EU level (section 7.3) include:

- (i) **regulate or provide incentives for the development of strategic asset management of water supply systems** for the prioritization of the most cost-effective investments on the long term, towards network renewal and smart monitoring, assessing the progress through quantity and quality indicators;
- (ii) **monitor and regulate, particularly in water-scarce regions**, the non-potable uses of drinking water (e.g., in the Lisbon LL, the water-smartness strategic plan developed using the developed Water Smartness Assessment Framework ([D6.3](#)) establishes mid-term and long-term targets for eliminating the drinking water use in non-potable municipal uses by considering alternative sources mostly water reuse).

Regarding **energy**, examples of recommendations at EU level (section 7.4) include:

- (i) promote and provide **the means for energy efficiency in water systems and self-sufficiency in WWTPs** towards energy neutrality as foreseen in the new Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD); as the example of biogas production for energy self-sufficiency in LLs Alicante and Venice LLs.
- (ii) regarding the **energy production and use by water utilities**, facilitate the management between the water systems and the energy distribution grid (e.g., provide guidance/make mandatory the energy contracts to safeguard both the uptake and the upload of energy by the water utility), in order to minimise the need for energy storage while ensuring the quality of electricity on the distribution grid;
- (iii) provide incentives for the **adoption of water-energy efficiency certificates** for housing (similar to the existing energy efficiency certificates, e.g. in the Lisbon LL);

A policy brief was issued on this topic and is available in [D5.8](#) as Policy brief #1. *Unleashing the untapped energy potential of wastewater - Recommendations for achieving the energy neutrality targets of the revised EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive.*

Concerning **recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others**, examples of recommendations at EU level (section 7.5) include:

- (i) co-produce an **EU roadmap for biosolids/sludge management**;
- (ii) revise the Council Directive 86/278/EEC concerning biosolids/sludge beneficial use in agriculture and the required characteristics/standards, defining a clearer allocation of responsibility along the biosolids value chain, involving the water utilities, the authorities and local actors in the development of circular solutions. Moreover, the inclusion in this legislation of clear requirements regarding the recovery of materials from biosolids/sludge is a way to overcome the existing barriers to circular economy, in contrast to a sludge management guided by legislation on waste;

- (iii) deliver a **comprehensive EU regulation concerning the organic fertilizers obtained from the urban wastewater treatment**, including the required characteristics/standards, to promote their recovery and market acceptance, correcting the barrier created by the exclusion of sewage sludge of the scope of the Fertilisers Regulation (2019/1009/EU);
- (iv) **promote monitoring of phosphorus (P)** as a critical raw material in Europe focusing on quality of materials with recovered phosphorus (e.g. biosolids and sludge) and accordingly update the regulation targets of phosphorus recovery, considering also **its beneficial use** through the irrigation with reclaimed water as suggested in water reuse topic (e.g. via Regulation (EU) 2020/741);
- (v) **promote research and the use of technologies that recover nutrients** (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) from wastewater and sludge streams in a concentrated form (e.g., the inorganic precipitate struvite), increasing the options for reuse with reduced pathogen risk and improved ease of transportation – regulation, such as the new UWWTD, can act as enabler for sludge treatment technology to evolve;
- (vi) better **harmonise the water, energy, and waste policies** at national, regional or local levels, namely to ensure coherence of policy and targets between biosolids recovery/beneficial use and biogas production, as identified in the Venice LL.

A policy brief was issued on this topic and is available in [D5.8](#) as Policy brief #3. *Applying Urban Wastewater and Sludge as Nutrients for Agriculture Use - Recommendations for EU Policy Reforms.*

Concerning **water reuse**, examples of recommendations at EU level (section 7.6) include:

- a future **revision of the Minimum requirements for water reuse, Regulation (EU) 2020/741**, which:
 - (i) extends its **scope to urban, industrial, and environmental uses**, establishing minimum requirements for industrial and urban uses, maintaining the fit-for-purpose principle used for agriculture uses;
 - (ii) reflects in the **monitoring** the knowledge about the system and its reliability;
 - (iii) accounts for **the beneficial use or recovery of phosphorus** through the irrigation with reclaimed water.
- developing a **strategic agenda on water reuse**, which:
 - (i) mandates the **integration of water reuse into EU water resources management** strategies and water resilience strategies (as foreseen in the new UWWTD);
 - (ii) reflects the best site-specific water resource management in the **cost coverage** of the additional treatment (if needed);
 - (iii) provides **guidelines** for **prioritizing the use of fresh and reclaimed water**;
 - (iv) provides **guidelines** on how to **account for indirect water reuse** (clarifying the boundaries between treated wastewater discharge and (indirect) water reuse);
 - (v) **accounts for environmental uses** as direct or indirect water reuse, e.g., for surface water augmentation or storage by **managed aquifer recharge**;
 - (vi) delivers **clear instructions** for a sound environmental impact assessment and health **risk assessment and management** of water reuse for aquifer recharge and surface water augmentation;
 - (vii) develop **guidelines** for a Europewide **coherent water reuse licensing and service provision**;

- (viii) promote research and **pilot demonstration projects of direct potable reuse to develop sound guidelines of water quality and treatment process operation** and redundancy needed to anticipate a solution for aggravated water scarcity, localised needs, emergency situations, as well as to build the trust of the society in water reuse safety (as conducted in Lisbon LL for food industry/beverage, in East Frisia LL in the dairy industry, and in Flanders LL for drinking water supply);
- (ix) promote research & innovation and subsequently develop **policy and regulation on water reuse business models, funding mechanisms, and pricing**, valuing opportunity costs and considering multiple users to improve **economic and technical** (e.g. decrease peak demands) **feasibility** of water reuse;
- (x) promote research and provide **guidance on how to upgrade the current urban WWTPs** to cope with the new requirements of the new UWWTD;
- (xi) fosters public **engagement**, raises **awareness**, and enhances **communication** on reclaimed water safety;
- (xii) encourages or mandates water organizations across Europe, including water utilities, municipalities, regulators and other stakeholders, to develop their own **strategic plans on water smartness** (as the six B-WaterSmart LLs did in the Innovation Alliance, T1.4), that should be supported by a **quantitative and objective-driven assessment framework** similar to that developed in B-WaterSmart, and should outline short-, medium- and long-term strategies and actions, and estimate the necessary human, technological, and financial resources required for implementation.

A policy brief was issued on this topic based on B-WaterSmart (Lisbon LL and also LLs Alicante, East Frisia, and Flanders) and also on Water-Minning projects and is available in [D5.8](#) as Policy brief #2. *Accelerating water smartness by successfully implementing the EU Water Reuse Regulation.*

Regarding stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses (as addressed in Flanders LL), recommendations cover governance and technical aspects, including:

- (i) promotion of stakeholders' **involvement in rain/stormwater management** as a shared challenge with a clear definition of roles, responsibility and ownership, including who and how to pay for an unstable source as stormwater;
- (ii) promotion of **storage and use of rainwater/stormwater in rural and urban** (including households) spaces;
- (iii) promotion of the **use of nature-based solutions to manage stormwater quantity and quality**;
- (iv) promotion of **smart monitoring and control of the water quality for the safety of the fit-for-purpose stormwater use** with the appropriate treatment.

The infrastructure aspects related to stormwater but also to other water-smart solutions are addressed in Policy brief #4. *Fostering circular water infrastructure - Boosting a circular water economy by creating an enabling environment for large-scale systems and infrastructure to support the development of alternative resources*, available in [D5.8](#).

1 Introduction

1.1. Objectives and scope

Within the scope of the B-WaterSmart WP5 – Society, Governance, and Policy, the objective of this document is to provide guidelines and recommendations for future policy and regulation instruments, according to the reality of each living lab, considering the drivers, barriers and socio-economic factors identified (Task 5.2 – analysis of drivers and barriers for implementation and acceptance of solutions), and the socioeconomic metrics developed for the water-smartness assessment framework (Task 6.2 – development of the water-smartness assessment framework). This includes policy recommendations aimed at creating an enabling environment for wide application of water-smart solutions, at local, national and EU levels. The guidelines consider contributions from the work developed in other activities of the project, particularly the referred drivers, barriers and socio-economic factors identified in Gomes et al. (2022) and Schmidt et al. (2023); from the strategic planning process developed within the B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance (InAll) presented in Cardoso et al. (2022) (Task 1.4 – implementing the B-WaterSmart innovation alliance InAll); the socioeconomic metrics developed in the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (Silva et al., 2023); the legal issues identified (Task 4.4 – supporting the circular transition: financing CE projects), including those hindering stormwater use in irrigation. Specific regulation and economic aspects, as economic incentive mechanism and instruments, as well as regulatory risk-related aspects of water reuse in agriculture were also addressed. In addition to the original plan, the results of an interactive discussion held in Alicante (September 2023), and of the Lisbon LL meeting dedicated to Policy & Regulation (January 2024) focused on water reuse and related issues are also included.

Drawing from the reality of representative case studies in the B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LLs) (Alicante|Spain, Bodo|Norway, East Frisia|Germany, Flanders|Belgium, Lisbon|Portugal, and Venice|Italy), the recommendations are expected to be applicable to other EU Members States and to support the production of a set of four policy briefs on regulation and policy instruments, targeted for improved policy frameworks at local, national and EU levels.

1.2. Structure

Following this introduction, Chapter 2 highlights the role of the policy and regulation instruments to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society, Chapter 3 identifies the scope of the recommendations, grounded on the B-WaterSmart resources addressed by the project LLs, and Chapter 4 describes the approach followed to produce the recommendations. This includes contributions from other project activities, as well as from an interactive session on policy and regulation (held in Alicante, ca. 70 project participants), and a dedicated Lisbon LL meeting (18 participants).

Chapter 5 maps the policy and regulation instruments, addressing water-related circularity, relevant for recommendations and with focus on B-WaterSmart resources, at European and LL levels, and addresses the different European directives and frameworks that currently govern water reuse. Where possible, it seeks to identify changes that can be expected. Additionally, it identifies the main issues and strengths to be addressed to achieve water-related circularity. It also provides a brief insight into the main challenges still facing water reuse for drinking water purposes and refers to current processes of reuse (e.g. via discharge in and abstraction from groundwater or surface water

bodies), technological possibilities, and quality standards. Chapter 6 analyses the major common and specific issues concerning policy and regulation. Chapter 7 presents the recommendations for policy and regulation.

2 Role of policy and regulation instruments to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society

2.1 Overview of key challenges in the transition to a water-smarter society

Relevant aspects in the transition to a water-smarter society are analysed in the literature (Damman et al. (2023) and an overview is presented in Cardoso et al. (2023). Together with the efficient use of resources (e.g. water and energy efficiency, control of water losses), the circular economy in water services intends to address issues of global, regional, and local sustainability, and is an issue of great relevance with an outstanding role in the sector's policies and strategic plans, both nationally and internationally. Internationally, there are several initiatives by funding agencies, regulators, and associations in the water sector. The initiative of the World Bank "Wastewater: From Waste to Resource" (World Bank, 2020) recognises the wastewater potential to create value and promotes shift in the paradigm in wastewater systems, replacing traditional wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) by resource recovery facilities, particularly for resources such as water, biosolids, energy, and fertiliser. The circular economy is highlighted on the Finnish Institute of the Environment research and development page (Syke, 2021), indicating to the four main areas of action that have been identified as key to sustainable water use: reducing inefficiencies in water use, reducing water losses, materials and energy recovery, and water recycling and reuse. To support management bodies, regulators, funding agencies, consultants, industry and researchers, the International Water Association (IWA) published, in 2016, a guide for circular economy in the urban water cycle, which is summarised in three interrelated resources, namely water, materials and energy (IWA, 2016). This association suggests that the urban water cycle should be considered and managed as a closed (circular) system, with cascading water quality options defined and differentiated for each use. It states that efficient reuse and transport systems are critical, to success, and that resource recovery should be competitive in a market driven by consumption. According to the IWA, the main challenge is to find markets willing to work with recovered products as alternatives to traditional (manufactured or extracted) products. Scale of production/recovery and acceptance by the consumer are identified as key problems. For the IWA, the energy portfolio should seek to increase renewable energy production and consumption, reducing fossil energy consumption, and contributing to zero carbon cities (IWA, 2016).

European Federation of National Water Services Associations has identified ten key challenges for the water sector for the next decade. One of these challenges is "Giving water its value in the circular economy". Wastewater and its by-products (e.g. sludge) contain valuable resources, such as energy and phosphorus, which can be recovered and reused, thus contributing to the conservation of scarce or depleted resources (and their associated negative impacts). Additionally, they may support job creation and economic growth, as jobs and incentives should be created to bring the recovered resources to the market in a sustainable way (EurEau, 2021). The new proposal for the EU urban wastewater treatment directive COM(2022)541 will require water utilities to systematically consider water reuse, reflecting the progress that has been made. In terms of energy, it proposes energy neutrality for urban wastewater treatment. In the context of the circular economy, WWTPs should be viewed as resource recovery facilities for water, energy, and materials (e.g. phosphorus), and managed accordingly.

In terms of stormwater management, there is a general dispersion of responsibilities in the stormwater sector worldwide. Clarification of financial models, greater articulation between agencies, and concern for environmental control are critical. International literature highlights the benefits of the green/blue approach, which should be implemented adaptively and progressively, taking advantage of investment opportunities to expand or rehabilitate systems (Ashley et al., 2020; Bertrand-Krajewski, 2020; Bichai and Ashbolt, 2017; EEA, 2017; Graham, 2016; Kapetas and Fenner, 2020; Zhou, 2014). The clear definition of stormwater systems boundaries is a relevant question for the allocation of responsibilities, for the definition of financing mechanisms, and for controlling services provision. Internationally, stormwater systems are generally regulated by environmental authorities, with a greater focus on flood protection, water bodies protection from pollution discharges, or increasing the resilience of cities to climate variability and uncertainty. All these aspects tend to focus on the downstream boundary. The European Directive 91/271/EEC on urban wastewater treatment (EU, 1991a) is currently under revision. The new proposal COM(2022)541 recommends to reduce pollution from stormwater in large agglomerations, requiring the implementation of integrated urban water management plans, where nature-based solutions are considered as good means to treat overflows (Zammar and Scholefield, 2021; Ashley et al. 2020; Bertrand-Krajewski, 2020; Bichai and Ashbolt, 2017; EEA, 2017; Graham, 2016; Kapetas and Fenner, 2020; Zhou, 2014).

An additional concern is the asset management of urban water systems, considered as an organisation coordinated activity to recognise and create value from its assets (ISO 55000:2014). Urban water systems belong to a significant portfolio of physical and other assets, which include the infrastructure that provides the service. Despite asset management is wider in terms of the issues it covers, infrastructure asset management (IAM) applied to urban water systems goes beyond the management of infrastructures as assets in themselves. It examines the specificities of the infrastructures, such as their interdependencies and the cause-effect relationship of their behaviour (Cardoso et al., 2023). IAM also intends to ensure the sustainability of these assets in the long term, guaranteeing compliance of the objectives and targets of the service over a longer time horizon and considering all dimensions of sustainability: social, environmental, and economic. It is also a powerful tool to address the integrated planning and management of all water services (the traditional water supply and wastewater management, as well as stormwater and water reuse). It should always be based on a sound strategic planning process, as exercised within the B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance (Task 1.4).

Regarding the digitalisation of water services, it is essential to recognise that there is an increasing number of actors with potential connections and possible motivations for intrusion, what may create concerns related to cybersecurity and security against intrusion. These motivations can be political, financial, economic, criminal or terrorist, among others (IDN, 2017). In this regard, it is already recommended within the framework of water security plans (IRAR, 2005) the existence of security systems against intrusion, particularly to avoid clandestine activities in reservoirs and catchment areas. The European Directive 2008/114/EC (ECI Directive) requires each Member State to identify potential critical infrastructures. These are infrastructures essential for the maintenance of functions vital to society, health, security, safety, or social well-being or economic and which disruption or destruction would have a major impact on a Member State. The transport and energy sectors are identified, but others may be included if considered appropriate. This Directive, which sets out obligations for the identification and designation of European Critical Infrastructures, has recently been revised and published, introducing additional measures for the protection of critical infrastructures (EU, 2022a).

2.2 Role of policy and regulation instruments to accelerate the transition

The water sector requires multi-level governance due to its cross-sectoral, geographic, and temporal interconnectedness (OECD, 2015). Effective freshwater management must consider both global and local scales, as hydrological and administrative boundaries often do not align, involving diverse stakeholders in decision-making, policy, and project cycles. Given water's nature as a capital-intensive natural monopoly with market shortcomings, coordination is essential (Hirano and Latorre, 2020; Lima et al., 2021; Cardoso et al., 2023). Water policy is inherently complex, impacting key areas such as health, environment, agriculture, and energy. As responsibilities shift to sub-national governments, strong intergovernmental coordination is needed to prevent policy fragmentation (OECD, 2015).

The water circular economy creates new challenges in water governance by adding water loops with various purposes and qualities, demanding robust institutional arrangements based on well-designed water policy frameworks and regulations, cooperative governance, the acknowledgement of risks and a fair distribution of benefits, costs, and risks (Riazi et al., 2023). The development of regulatory frameworks for water reuse may help to address safety concerns and support its adoption (Mukherjee and Jensen, 2020).

The Principles on Water Governance (OECD, 2015) aim at enhancing water governance systems that help to manage “water in a sustainable, integrated and inclusive way, at an acceptable cost, and in a reasonable timeframe”, recognising that governance is highly contextual, that water policies need to be tailored to different water resources and places, and that governance responses must adapt to changing circumstances.

Urgent action is needed to ensure environmental sustainability due to accelerating biodiversity loss, climate change impacts, and resource overuse OECD (2023). In OECD countries, regulation is the most used environmental policy tool (WAREG, 2021), including command-and-control measures and performance standards, which should be complemented by market-based instruments like taxes and permits, as well as incentives and self-regulation. A well-designed regulatory environment is crucial for encouraging innovation that supports environmental resilience while preventing harmful developments.

Exemplifying, the role of regulation creates an incentive for firms to invest in innovation with the aim of reducing compliance costs, for the case of environmental taxation that increases price of pollution, waste, and energy (Ren and Albrecht, 2023). A demonstration with this regard is that patenting activities from 1970 to 1994 were examined concluding that elevated energy prices resulting from increased energy taxation prompted firms to develop energy-efficient technologies (Popp, 2002). Furthermore, the most recent CE Action Plan (COM, 2020) advocates the broader implementation of environmental taxation (including waste taxes) to expedite the circular transition. Another example relates to wastewater effluent taxation applied in various EU countries. As mentioned in Salminen et al. (2022), while the rationale and magnitude for the tax varies across countries, the collected revenue is typically allocated to measures for improving water quality and other investments in water supply and environmental protection (European Commission, 2016). A demonstration according to Müller-Gulland et al. (2015) is that the wastewater tax has been effective in reducing emissions of harmful pollutants into water bodies in Germany, also leading to the development of treatment technologies for industrial wastewater.

The development of agile, technology-neutral, and adaptive regulation promotes innovation and contributes to mitigate innovation-related risks, including for climate and the environment (Mukherjee and Jensen, 2020; OECD, 2021a; Riazi et al., 2023). When there is significant risk, rules are required addressing the factors that can lead to harm, and permitting requirements, inspections and enforcement must depend on the level of risk of a given product, issue, and business (OECD, 2021b). Additionally, precautionary measures as environmental licensing or prohibition need to be balanced with the societal benefits of environmental action and innovations. Permitting, or licensing, is a regulatory tool for public administrations to regulate the registration and/or operation of a business unit by prior approval. It includes all requirements needed by the operator to start their activity (approvals, permits, licenses, certifications, professional requirements, authorisations of all types). In the case of environmental policy, improving licensing and permitting procedures can promote green innovation by enabling businesses to carry out environmentally friendly activities (OECD, 2021b).

At the European level, the development and implementation of EU policies include the European Commission laws' proposals to the European Parliament and Council of the EU, helping Member States implementing EU legislation, managing the EU's budget, and allocating funding, ensuring that EU law is complied with. EU policies are designed to bring benefits to citizens, businesses, and other stakeholders in the EU. Better regulation tools ensure that each new policy is based on evidence and best available practice (EC-SP, 2023). The Better Regulation agenda (COM (2015)215) ensures that EU policymaking is evidence-based, leading to simpler and better EU laws, while avoiding unnecessary burdens. It involves citizens, businesses, and stakeholders in the decision-making process.

EU water policy is one of the foundations of environmental protection in the EU, with the rules to protect water resources, fresh and saltwater ecosystems, and ensure drinking and bathing water are clean. In the context of the European Green Deal, the Water Framework Directive (EU, 2000) provides the main framework and the objectives for water policy in Europe.

Gomes et al. (2022) highlight water as a current pressing concern for EU policy, in line with its Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, the Green Deal, the Territorial Agenda 2030 and the 'Farm to Fork' Strategy (aiming to promote more sustainable, fair, and more resilient food systems in the EU, while protecting biodiversity). Water is also a critical sector for investment under New Generation EU and the national Recovery and Resilience Plans, which also respond to the social and economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemics.

An overview of the key policy strategies driving a smart-water society in Europe is presented in Gomes et al. (2022), focusing on the areas of climate action and circular economy, in line with the United Nations Agenda for 2030, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement. They feature the main points of convergence between adaptation and circular economy policy, as well as water-related EU directives, key European policy strategies that have been updated over the last few years.

Overall, the EU commitments to the Water Action Agenda aim to achieve (EC-ECCE, 2023): i) water security for all, global resilience to water stress; ii) the human right to safe drinking water and sanitation, without compromising the rights of future generations; iii) protected and restored aquatic ecosystems; and iv) a fair balance between water supply and demand.

The first EU Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), launched in 2015 by the EC, considered five priority areas: plastics, food waste, critical raw materials, construction and demolition, and biomass and bio-based products. As a demonstration of its accelerator role to the transition to a circular economy in Europe, all 54 actions are either completed or being implemented. EU key outcomes include a 6% rise in circular employment from 2012 to 2016; 155 billion euros in value-added from circular activities in 2017, a 17% increase from 2011; and significant increase in municipal waste recycling from 2008 to 2016 (OECD, 2020).

The new EU CEAP (EC, 2020) aims at facilitating water reuse and efficiency (including in industrial processes) and announced the review of directives on wastewater treatment and sewage sludge, and the development of an Integrated Nutrient Management Plan to ensure more sustainable application of nutrients and stimulate the markets for recovered nutrients. Among the CEAP priorities is the new Water Reuse Regulation (EU, 2020a) to encourage circular approaches to water reuse in agriculture.

To demonstrate the role of policies, Member States have responded to the CEAPs adopting CE policies. Twenty countries have adopted national CE policies until 2022 and, due to the Green Deal, sixteen countries explicitly linked CE and climate policies (EEA, 2022). As examples, the generation of municipal waste in Spain has gradually decreased since 2018. This decline is linked to the implementation of measures like the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy and the Circular Economy Action Plan (2021–2023). These efforts are starting to show results, particularly in reducing waste generation, suggesting the positive impact of these policies. Based on the 2021 assessment, the degree of fulfilment of the objectives of Portugal's National Action Plan for the Circular Economy (PAEC) 2018–2020 is presenting, among other macro activities, very satisfactory improvements in the action of regenerating resources – water and nutrients, namely water efficiency, water reuse, and recirculation of nutrients and organic matter through their natural cycles. Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan includes the reform of the Integrated and Circular Management of Water Resources in Situations of Scarcity, which plans investment in promoting the circular use of water resources using treated wastewater (EEA, 2022).

Recently, general considerations on water stress have been integrated into the European Green Deal, the biodiversity strategy for 2030, the farm to fork strategy, the 2030 climate and energy framework, the new circular economy action plan, and the 2050 long-term strategy. Elements of water security and insurance are also embedded in the EU's sustainable finance taxonomy (EEA, 2021). Developing comprehensive and incentive regulatory frameworks and incentive pricing mechanisms is as important for facilitating the uptake of new technologies as developing the technical solutions themselves (EEA, 2021). However, the water and water-related management still needs to be developed in CE policy and regulation. The recent, or still pending, update of key directives, such as the Drinking Water Quality Directive (Directive (EU) 2020/2184) (EU, 2020) and the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive recast (COM(2022)541) (EC, 2022) is expected to leverage the adoption of innovative solutions in water systems (e.g., analytical services, digitalization, technology supply). These updated directives establish new ambitious targets for water quality, including contaminants of emerging concern, water efficiency and water losses control, energy neutrality, water reuse, nutrients recovery, and stormwater management.

Within the scope of B-WaterSmart, P&R instruments play an important role to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society. The circular economy (CE) challenges bring together several policy and regulatory regimes with potential gaps and overlaps. This may restrict the feasibility of circular water

solutions. As the CE requires a shift from waste management and disposal towards the value creation within and between sectors, it is fundamental that pressures between different regulatory frameworks are overcome. Furthermore, it is important that they drive progress.

For instance, in Portugal, the Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority (ERSAR) is responsible for the economic regulation and quality of service regulation. They complement each other and constitute forms of the behavioural regulation of the water utilities. The quality of the service regulation, in place since 2004 (first generation of the assessment system) and having periodical (5-year) critical revisions, has been in the last two decades the instrument best suited to encourage the utilities to achieve the service quality objectives (Cardoso et al., 2023). It proved its leading role in the Portuguese success of water services reform towards water supply and pollution abatement. For example, from 1993 to 2017 (Baptista, 2018), the numbers shifted from 81% to 96% population with public water supply services, 50% to 99.1% safe water according to the EU directives, 630 to 8 hepatitis A cases per year, 28% to 83% population with public wastewater services, 22% to 100% population with urban waste management services, 28% to 78% good quality surface water according to the EU directives, 55% to 99% coastal beaches with good quality bathing water, 17% to 95% river beaches with good quality bathing water, 89 to 289 blue-flag beaches, 87 to 293 golden beaches (EEA, 2017). Nowadays, the quality-of-service regulation is having a pioneering role in preparing the water sector to address the new challenges introduced by the latest EU policy developments in drinking water (EU, 2020b), urban wastewater treatment (EC, 2022), cybersecurity, water resilience and circular economy (EC, 2020). The current 4th generation of the assessment system, developed in 2021 (aligned with the national Portuguese strategic plan for the decade, for water, wastewater, and stormwater services — PENSAARP 2030) integrates key performance indicators (KPIs) on Safe drinking water, Real water losses Emergency and stormwater discharges control, Sewer pipes condition monitoring, Service coverage including small agglomerations, Reclaimed water production as a function of water scarcity, Treatment sludge production, Energy self-sufficiency, Security and Resilience Indexes for water supply and wastewater management, Cost recovery and infrastructure sustainability (e.g., Rehabilitation, and Adequacy of treatment capacity) (Cardoso et al., 2021, 2023; Rosa et al., 2025). Many of these KPIs were adopted by or inspired the B-WaterSmart assessment framework (Silva et al., 2023).

3 Water-related resources addressed in B-WaterSmart

For definition of the scope for the policy and regulation recommendations, the resources addressed by the B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LLs) – Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, and Venice – were considered the most relevant within the project focus. Based on the LL strategic agendas agreed by the Communities of Practice (CoPs) (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023), the identification of the resources addressed by LLs in the project is presented in Table 1. CoPs are communities formed by people who voluntarily share common interest, interact regularly, exchange information and knowledge, and seek to sustain the community and share learning (Rebelo et al., 2021).

Table 1. Resources addressed in the B-WaterSmart LLs

Type of resource /circularity	Living Labs addressing the resource in B-WaterSmart	# related B-WaterSmart product or tool (Annex 1)
Digitalisation & IoT	All LLs	Digital tools
Drinking water	Bodø: Urban water losses management	#14, #15, #29, #30
	East Frisia: Regional water demand-supply matching tool, Short-term demand forecasting tool, UWOT tool	#22, #23, #28
Energy	Alicante: Biogas production and microturbines for energy self-sufficiency	#10, #13
	Bodø: Small-scale biogas production	#12
	Lisbon: W-E-P balance, climate readiness certification	#17, #24, #25, #33
	Venice: Biogas production and energy saving	#4, #11
Nutrients, biosolids and others	Alicante: Ammonia recovery, biosolids beneficial use, Cl ₂ production	#7, #8, #9
	Venice: Ammonia recovery, Biosolids beneficial use	#11, #19
Reclaimed water	Alicante: Reclaimed water production for urban uses and industry	#18
	East Frisia: Water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate	#6
	Flanders: Regional analysis, agricultural reuse Direct potable reuse	#2, #3, #5, #22, #26, #31
	Lisbon: Reclaimed water for non-potable urban uses Direct potable reuse for beer production	#1, #17, #20, #24, #25, #27
	Venice: Reclaimed water for industrial and agricultural reuse	#4, #16, #32
Stormwater	Flanders: Agricultural use (Proef Station)	#21, #22, #26
Cross-cutting	All LLs: Water-smartness assessment framework and tool	#34

4 Approach

4.1 Overview

The approach adopted (Figure 1) includes contributions from the work developed in other activities of the project, namely (i) drivers, barriers and socio-economic factors identified in Gomes et al. (2022) and Schmidt et al. (2023), (ii) the SWOT analyses from the strategic planning process developed within the B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance (InAll) (Cardoso et al., 2022); (iii) the socioeconomic metrics developed in the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (Silva et al., 2023); (iv) the legal issues identified in Task 4.4, including stormwater use for irrigation. Specific regulation and economic aspects, as economic incentive mechanism and instruments, as well as regulatory risk-related aspects of water reuse in agriculture were also envisaged. In addition to the original plan, the approach also includes the results of an interactive discussion held in Alicante, during the project meeting on the 19th of September 2023, and of the Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation focused on water reuse and related issues, that took place on the 12th of January 2024.

Figure 1. Approach adopted to develop the recommendations.

4.2 Contributions from B-WaterSmart developments

4.2.1 Contributions from WP4, WP5 and WP6

The work carried out includes the analysis of information from other project developments and deliverables (Gomes et al., 2022; Schmidt et al., 2023 and Silva et al., 2023), as well as new information to complement this analysis. The set of questions in Table 2 was proposed to support the gathering of information needed to produce the P&R recommendations and the subsequent policy briefs, guiding the analysis of the deliverables, and encouraging further contributions. The contributions are integrated in the mapping of policy and regulation instruments (section 5.3).

Table 2. Questions proposed to guide the gathering of information.

<p><i>Remark: please consider information regarding EU, national, and local reports; relevant LL legislation, governmental plans, or central actions; Best Management Practices, guidelines, other relevant instruments (for EU, national and local levels). Key-aspects to address are land use, water use/reuse including stormwater, energy production, pricing, market, multilevel actors, contracts' mechanisms, agreements or memoranda of understanding, allocation of responsibilities.</i></p>	
<p>Regulations and Policy Practices addressing water circularity in LL X (Country X) (Analysis per LL)</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there national policy frameworks or instruments supporting the implementation of the B-WaterSmart solutions for this country? (Identify them linking to the solutions addressed) 2. Are there national legislative frameworks supporting the implementation of the B-WaterSmart solutions for this country? (Identify them linking to the solutions addressed) 3. Are there local/sub-national legislation and policies supporting the implementation of the B-WaterSmart solutions for this LL? (Identify them linking to the solutions addressed) 4. Considering national and local legislation in this country/LL, are there gaps or inconsistencies between EU regulation and national or local legislation? (Identify them linking to the solutions addressed) 5. Can you outline and B-WaterSmart the most significant legal and policy barriers that hinder the implementation of the BWS solutions, differentiating between the B-WaterSmart solutions for this country/LL? 6. Can you identify the political level(s) at which legal and policy barriers may be most severe (EU/International, national, federal, and local)? 7. Does the legal and policy situation support or impair interventions for exploiting the B-WaterSmart solutions for this country/LL? If so, what barriers apply? 8. What legal and policy barriers impede successful business models for the B-WaterSmart solutions in this country/LL? 	
<p>Policy and legal drivers and approaches to overcome barriers in LL X (Country X) (Analysis per LL)</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Can you outline and describe the most significant legal and policy drivers, factors that support water circularity, differentiating between the B-WaterSmart solutions for this country/LL? 10. Which requirements or needs do you consider most critical for improving the legal and policy framework creating an enabling environment for water circularity and implementation of the B-WaterSmart solution for this country/LL? 11. What governmental or private sector actors do you consider most critical for improving the legal and policy framework for water circularity and implementation of B-WaterSmart solutions for this country/LL? 12. Are there actor-based instruments (such as a central agency to coordinate interventions, a quality of service or environmental regulator, or specific funding or educational programmes) established that promote water circularity and support the implementation of B-WaterSmart solutions for this country/LL? If yes, please specify. 13. Are there legal and policy interventions that are currently being planned, revised or already under way to overcome the main barriers you mentioned above (e.g., a revision of quality-of-service assessment system?) 	

4.2.2 Contributions from WP1 InAll partners | strategic planning

One of the objectives of the Innovation Alliance (Task 1.4) was to build the capacity of the LL problem-owners' organizations on developing a strategic planning process towards water smartness, while promoting sharing and cross-fertilisation among the InAll partners (Rebelo et al., 2021). The process follows a 5-phased schedule program (Figure 2; Cardoso et al., 2022). In Phase 3 – Diagnosis, a SWOT analysis was carried out by the problem-owners (highlighted in blue in Figure 2), where the main Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats were identified. The policy and regulation aspects identified in each LL were used as an input for the recommendations.

[text in green] plan related tasks, (steps not to be carried out by those LLs producing a strategic agenda rather than a strategic plan)

Figure 2: The InAll process | 5-phased schedule program (Cardoso et al., 2022)

4.3 Interactive session on Policy & Regulation

4.3.1 General overview

The Policy & Regulation (P&R) interactive session took place on the 19th of September 2023, as part of the project PSB meeting in Alicante (Spain). It aimed to contribute to identify relevant recommendations for policy and regulation, resource-oriented and addressing different scales, i.e., EU/national/regional/local. It was planned to share the work carried out within B-WaterSmart, with contribution of the Living Labs regarding the P&R instruments and issues identified for the following

types of resources addressed in the B-WaterSmart LLs: **1. Digitalisation and IoT; 2. Drinking water; 3. Energy; 4. Nutrients, biosolids, and others; 5. Reclaimed water; and 6. Stormwater.**

4.3.2 Working tables organization

The work session was organized into these six working tables, each one addressing a different topic or type of resource, to focus the 50-min discussion on the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations. Seventy participants attended this session (sixty partners and ten members of the advisory board). Each participant selected a table according to his/her main interests, ensuring the participation from the LLs and other partners, and distributing elements from the same organization among different tables. As there were not enough participants for the Energy table, the worktables were organized as presented in Table 3. The session was supported by LNEC's and ICS-UL's teams, and by Maria Salvetti, the Project Advisory Board member who accompanies WP5 more directly.

Table 3. Working tables organization

Topic Type of resource /circularity	Participants
1. Digitalisation and IoT Facilitator: Carla Gomes (ICS-UL)	16 Total 16 3 LL owners 3 4 R&D 4 9 Tech. providers and others 9
2. Drinking water Facilitator: Helena Alegre (LNEC)	Total 15 LL owners 5 R&D 8 Tech. providers and others 2
4. Nutrients, biosolids and others Facilitator: Rita Ribeiro (LNEC)	Total 8 R&D + LL mentor 4 Tech. providers and others 4
5. Reclaimed water Facilitator: Maria João Rosa (LNEC)	Total 17 LL owners 5 R&D 6 Tech. providers and others 6
6. Stormwater Facilitator: Maria Adriana Cardoso (LNEC)	Total 11 LL owners 4 R&D 5 Tech. providers and others 2

In each worktable, the involved LLs indicated the major P&R issues for the topic. After discussion, each table identified three major issues and, for each, the “Policy & Regulation Recommendations” on the “white board”. Each recommendation was tentatively classified regarding scales (EU, National, Regional, local) and PESTLE dimensions (Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)). The results are presented in Annex 2 (as provided by the participants) and in section 5.3 (after LNEC team analysis).

4.3.3 Ranking of topics

Using the Mentimeter online collaborative tool, each participant individually ranked the six topics, according to the relevance for the future the B-WaterSmart policy briefs. The same ranking was carried out by each LL. The results are presented in Annex 2 and discussed in section 7.8.

4.4 Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation focused on water reuse and related-issues

The Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation was part of the LL developments of B-WaterSmart in Lisbon (Portugal) and took place on the 12th of January 2024. It aimed to discuss several aspects related to water reuse to contribute to identify relevant recommendations for policy and regulation. It was attended by eighteen participants: four from the Lisbon Municipality (LL owner), four from LNEC (LL mentor), one from ICS-UL (WP5 leader, observer), eight regulator experts (environmental regulation; water and wastewater services regulation), and a lawyer. The set of ten questions prepared by LNEC (Table 4) was discussed.

Table 4. Set of questions for discussion | Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation

General question applicable from 1-10	
Is it necessary to legislate or regulate at European, national, or local level...?	
Q1	other uses of reclaimed water (e.g. urban)
Q2	indirect reuse
Q3	emission limits vs. capacity of receiving body and intended uses
Q4	aquifer recharge
Q5	evolution in minimum quality requirements for various uses and monitoring
Q6	prioritize reclaimed water uses in licensing
Q7	allow distribution/sale of reclaimed water to third parties, by licensed users
Q8	autonomize/regulate the reclaimed water supply service
Q9	evolution of economic regulation, namely development of legal and regulatory instruments for the formation of tariffs for reclaimed water supply activity
Q10	relevance of the existence of strategic planning

5 Policy and regulation instruments on water-related circularity addressed in B-WaterSmart

5.1 Overview of EU instruments

5.1.1 General

In the last decades, water policy in Europe has been developed progressively (Figure 3) (WISE, 2023). In 1991, the first EU policies aimed at improving water quality by adopting the Urban Wastewater Treatment (91/271/EEC) and Nitrates (91/676/EEC) Directives (EU, 1991a, 1991b), with the objective of reducing pollution pressures to water. In 2000, an integrated ecosystem-based approach to managing water was introduced by the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC) (EU, 2000). The Drinking Water (98/83/EC), Bathing Water (06/7/EC) and Floods (2007/60/EC) Directives (EU, 1998, 2006, 2007), were adopted to ensure public safety and health objectives. In 2020, the water reuse regulation addressing the minimum requirements for water reuse for agricultural irrigation has entered into force, in the context of the new Circular Economy Action Plan adopted in 2020 (WISE, 2023).

Figure 3. Overview of the European water-related policies (WISE, 2023)

While the Directives tend to be very specific, the importance of water in relation to biodiversity and marine policies is pursued through the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 (EC, 2020a) and the priority objectives of the 8th European Action Program (EU, 2022b). Water quantity remains an area of national competence, although issues linked to overall sustainable water use are of transboundary and thus European interest (EC, 2011b).

The Green Deal (COM(2019) 640 final) is a key European policy to enhance the full implementation of the existing environmental legislation, including the water-related directives summarised in Figure 3. In addition, it proposes a green European Union that supports the global ambition of ensuring that all the ecosystems are restored, resilient, and adequately protected by 2050 (WISE 2023). It is a new strategy that aims to protect, conserve, and enhance the EU's natural capital, and protect the health and well-being of citizens from environment-related risks and impacts. It commits to the implementation of the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy, Zero Pollution Action Plan, Farm to Fork Strategy, Circular Economy Action Plan, Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, and Climate

Adaptation Strategy (including Climate Law), all water related. The European Climate Law (i) writes into law the goal set out in the European Green Deal for Europe's economy and society to become climate-neutral by 2050 (net zero greenhouse gas emissions), (ii) sets the intermediate target of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, (iii) aims to ensure that all EU policies contribute to this goal and that all sectors of the economy and society play their part. As additional legislation is adopted, further targets and initiatives will come, as the new EU strategy for water resilience planned to be launched in March 2024.

5.1.2 Regulatory and legal barriers for the water reuse in agriculture for irrigation

Indirect water reuse for agricultural irrigation is widespread. During dry conditions, treated wastewater constitutes a significant flow component in many surface water bodies, especially in smaller streams located near wastewater treatment plants (Beard et al., 2019). Direct water reuse, on the other hand, has been practiced in several Mediterranean countries but is still uncommon in large parts of the EU.

Water reuse in agriculture has long been practiced worldwide (for historical reference, see Jaramillo and Restrepo 2017). What is new is the ways in which reuse is being (re)considered in policy and regulation. In 1992, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) established guidelines for water reuse in agriculture (Pescod 1992). Focusing on health protection, these guidelines include effluent quality standards and threshold levels of trace elements for crop production. It then provides an indication of the types of wastewater treatment that are expected to achieve the required microbiological quality. It also lists specific concerns and measures for wastewater reuse in aquaculture. Also, in light of the Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG targets 6.3 (Water quality and wastewater) and 6.4 (water use and scarcity), increased attention is paid to the potential of reuse.

As part of the European Green Deal, the EU Action Plan for Circular Economy (European Commission, 2020) pushes European policies towards circularity. While water has until recently received relatively little attention (compared to, for example, solid waste management), the EU Action Plan does anticipate the implementation of new regulations for water reuse and nutrient management. Hence, a significant aspect of moving towards a circular economy will involve the further technological and practice development of water reuse and recovery of nutrients from wastewater.

To this effect, policies and regulations can both facilitate and constrain the development and implementation of water reuse practices, and clarity in policies and regulation is key to its successful uptake (Frijns et al., 2016).

A major regulatory obstacle to reuse has been that wastewater, as well as substances extracted from wastewater, may retain their status as 'waste' even after treatment. The EU directive on waste (directive 2006/12/EC) states that 'waste' means any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard. However, wastewater is explicitly excluded from the scope of this directive. A key question to reuse, then, is how and under what conditions, water may change status from 'waste' to 'resource'.

5.1.3 European legislation and directives on stormwater and brown water reuse in agriculture

The WFD (Directive 2000/60/EC) establishes a legal framework to protect and restore clean water in the EU and to ensure its long-term sustainable use. The WFD does not include irrigation requirements, nor is there a specific irrigation water directive to address agricultural water use. However, operating under the WFD, several other directives regulate the use and reuse of water for irrigation purposes. Because agricultural irrigation is directly linked to the chemical status of groundwater and surface water bodies, the Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC), the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (2008/105/EC), as well as the Bathing Water Directive (2006/7/EC), are all relevant frameworks within which water-smart solutions for agriculture must operate.

The Groundwater Directive against pollution and deterioration provides specific criteria for the assessment of good chemical status, while threshold values for pollutants (apart from nitrates and pesticides) are set by the Member States. This is relevant to reuse practices so far as reclaimed water will be infiltrated, rather than discharged into surface water bodies, and to the extent that irrigation water is expected to infiltrate into groundwater layers. In similar, the Nitrates Directive seeks to protect surface waters from nitrates from agricultural sources, safeguarding drinking water and preventing damage from eutrophication. In the implementation of reuse practices, it will be interesting to assess to what extent the nitrates present in reclaimed water might reduce the need for additional fertilizers.

The management of urban wastewater (including domestic, industrial, and rainwater runoff) is stipulated in the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC). This directive provides the conditions under which urban wastewater may be discharged into the environment. Interestingly, the original 1991 text of the directive already stated that: “Treated waste water shall be reused whenever appropriate. Disposal routes shall minimize the adverse effects on the environment” (Art. 12.1). However, how, when, and under what conditions wastewater may be reused is not further specified.

This is changing with the adoption of the Water Reuse Regulation (Regulation EU 2020/741), which is the first European regulatory framework that directly addresses water reuse, and which applies since June 2023. This regulation addresses the reuse of treated urban wastewater for agricultural irrigation. Harmonizing the minimum requirements for reclaimed water at a European level is considered vital to the efficient functioning of the internal market with regard to agricultural products. While the Wastewater Directive requires that wastewater is properly treated before reuse, the Water Reuse Regulation requires that the treated wastewater is of sufficient quality for safe and sustainable reuse.

When it comes to the regulation of water (re)use, the quality of the water is naturally the key concern, as it is associated with human and environmental health. Hence, the Reuse Regulation provides the minimum requirements for water quality and monitoring. These are framed primarily as obligations of the treatment and reclamation facility operator. In addition, the Reuse Regulation outlines risk management requirements. This includes the requirement that the competent authorities (as designated by the Member States) must establish “water reuse risk management plans” in collaboration with the reclamation facility operator, other responsible parties, and end-users.

Besides providing a framework of minimum quality requirements for reclaimed water in agriculture, the regulation also stipulates that “reclamation facility operators and the end-users should cooperate

to ensure that reclaimed water meets the needs of the end-users regarding crop categories” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2020: 35). The implications of this in practice have not yet fully crystallized. It suggests that reuse initiatives should be adapted to particular types of agricultural production where possible.

Several European countries have been reusing effluents already before the EU regulation came into force (notably Malta, Cyprus, and Spain). This demonstrates that reusing water has been a viable option within the existing European legislative frameworks but has remained dependent on national and regional initiatives. The Water Reuse Regulation remains fairly non-committal in this regard, considering that it is supposed to provide “an enabling framework for those Member States who wish or need to practice water reuse,” which should ensure that it is possible for Member States “to apply those rules when they decide to introduce this practice at a later stage” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2020: 33). However, the key change that can be expected from the Reuse Regulation is that Member States must now provide justification for the decision not to reuse water for agricultural purposes in certain basins, for example due to pressures on, or the status of, water resources. Member States also remain responsible for the designation of the competent authorities and deadlines, for designing the appropriate procedures for permits, for setting up the necessary administrative infrastructures, and for establishing appropriate penalties for infringements of the Regulation.

5.1.4 Next Steps: Towards Direct Potable Water Reuse?

An important caveat of the European Water Reuse Regulation is that it considers alternative irrigation sources for agriculture and horticulture, but does not address other forms of water reuse, such as reuse for human consumption or beverage production. The minimum requirements listed in the Regulation do not apply (at least not explicitly) to drinking water purposes. For drinking water, the Regulation refers to the water quality requirements intended for human consumption as laid down in Directive (EU) 2020/2184. However, the Reuse Regulation does outline the **requirements for ‘Class A’** reclaimed water, which should be of sufficient quality to irrigate crops consumed raw, and where the edible parts are in direct contact with the reclaimed water. These ‘Class A’ requirements still differ from the minimum requirements of drinking water (e.g., the parametric value of E-coli in Class A water is $\leq 10 / 100\text{ml}$, and 0 in drinking water). In short, the Reuse Regulation does not provide guidelines suitable to provide direction towards direct potable reuse.

Currently, most industrial, and urban wastewater streams are, after treatment, discharged in surface water or used for the replenishment of groundwater. As a result, a significant part of the available surface water is influenced by the outflow of wastewater treatment plants and industrial effluents (Beard, 2019). As surface water is extracted for treatment or irrigation purposes, indirect water reuse for both agricultural and potable uses is already common practice.

Direct Potable Reuse (DPR) does not use the environment (surface water or aquifers) as buffers between discharge and extraction.

Figure 4 exemplifies how in indirect potable reuse, water changes status from the moment of extraction, through treatment, distribution, and use, to collection as brown or sewage water, and is afterwards as effluent discharged back into the environment.

DPR is represented by the orange arrows. A DPR cycle would 'skip' the discharge and subsequent extraction steps, which means the legal status of the water needs to change along with it: from 'waste' or 'effluent' to 'resource'.

Figure 4: Indirect and direct potable reuse

DPR is already being practiced in several countries outside the EU, including Namibia, South Africa, Australia, Singapore, and the United States. Case studies from these countries show that treated wastewater is in most cases blended with newly extracted surface or groundwater, thus presenting a combination of indirect and direct potable reuse (Aleksić and Šušteršič, 2022).

In the EU, DPR is still uncommon. While the Reuse Regulation does not address reuse for consumption, it does underscore that the water reuse risk management plans “should pay special attention to the protection of water bodies used for the abstraction of water intended for human consumption” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2020: 34). Similarly, the Drinking Water Directive requires that the source of drinking water must be protected and kept free from contaminants that could impact its quality. Considering this, the current policy and regulation landscape of the EU does not yet encourage potable reuse. However, as noted, the minimum quality standards are leading and do not exclude treated wastewater as a source.

5.2 Circular business model innovation and policy and regulation

5.2.1 General aspects, impact of regulation on circular business model innovation

A circular business model (CBM) is a sustainable business model offering solutions that create ecological value, protect the environment and are economically viable. It optimises products along the entire value chain, reducing environmental impacts. CBM has great potential to catalyse a paradigm shift towards sustainable development (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017).

In the context of the B-WaterSmart project circular business models were defined and used in Barrero et al. (2021) (D4.1), (Flores et al., 2024) (D4.3) and Pérez et al. (2024) (D4.4) as “the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value with slowing, closing, or narrowing flows of the resource loops” (Oghazi and Mostaghel, 2018).

Circular business models require a regulatory environment that facilitates their implementation through incentive mechanisms, quality standards, and clear rules for the efficient use of water resources. Policies and regulations have a direct impact on the selection of solutions and value chains proposed in CBMs. This shows the importance of policy and regulation in CBMs for a transition to a more circular and sustainable mode of operation, since the extent to which sustainable principles are incorporated into the design of CBMs depends on the ambition of decision-makers.

Regulatory factors will have a substantial impact on the innovation of circular business models, a trend expected to intensify as future business model innovation becomes increasingly influenced by technological advancements, data-driven strategies, and ecosystem-based movements. Regulation tends to impede innovation efficiency, particularly in highly uncertain markets (Nielsen, 2023, Aghion et al., 2021) indicating a correlation between regulation and lower innovation intensity. However, there are positive instances where direct environmental regulation creates new markets for innovative solutions, driven by increased demand for clean energy technologies, and intellectual property laws incentivize firms to invest in research and development. Indirect forms of regulation, such as those preventing established companies from stifling competition, can create opportunities for new entrants with innovative business models. Nevertheless, challenges may arise if regulations hinder firms from experimenting with new models or diminish incentives for risk-taking. Additionally, the speed of legislative adaptation to new technologies and the influence of indirect regulation on social norms impacting consumer behaviour are identified as critical factors shaping future business model innovation (Nielsen, 2023).

In highly regulated contexts, such as the water sector, the establishment of Water-Oriented Living Labs creates very effective environments for collaborative innovation among public authorities, water companies, technological and solution providers, and research institutes. These environments enable the analysis and assessment of the impacts of current policies and regulations on the development of circular solutions, facilitating adjustments and modifications to foster the adoption of technologies that promote circular solutions and the consequent development of circular business models.

Therefore, LLs are large-scale innovation environments that select, connect and demonstrate smart technologies, management and data solutions for new business models based on the circular economy and smart water management. LLs can promote environmental sustainability through economic value, material and knowledge flows in the CE (Kallai et al., 2020). LLs emphasise the role of user involvement in the creation of new technologies, services, products or systems (Engez et al., 2021). Urban LLs are used for environmental sustainability and CE, to regenerate neighbourhoods, support CBMs and promote social innovation (Filho et al., 2022).

The 6 LLs in the B-WaterSmart project, selected for their complementarity and mutual learning opportunities, act as experimental environments where circular business models are developed, tested, and validated in the context of water management. The key aspect of CBM-LL connection is that LLs are not only platforms for technological innovation but also provide a practical space to adjust and adapt business models to the realities of the existing regulatory framework and local

needs. This is achieved through the practical analysis of existing policies and their impact on the economic feasibility of these models, identifying which regulations encourage or hinder their application. More information on developing and implementing CBMs for each LL in B-WaterSmart is presented in Pérez et al. (2024) (D4.4).LLs have the capacity to experiment, innovate, and explore, yet they require support systems to ensure sustained success and longevity. The shift towards a circular economy necessitates not only heightened business, technological, and social innovation but also collaboration and strategies involving governments, companies, and citizens collectively. These crucial collaborative efforts and strategies can be termed as enablers for the circular economy (ETC, 2021).

In this line, efficient circular economy policies can encourage the uptake of suitable business models, technical innovations, and social changes by offering the needed stimuli to unleash their potential for the transition. In this context, policy encompasses actions taken or suggested by legislative and executive bodies to facilitate and hasten circular initiatives (ETC, 2021). The following policy tools are considered: Legislative measures, regulations, and information requirements (e.g. EU Ecodesign Directive, restrictions on the use of hazardous substances), support for research and innovation, economic incentive mechanisms (environmental taxation), voluntary tools and guidelines (EU Ecolabel or the EU green public procurement criteria).

Clear policies, including specific targets and proper enforcement, can aid, prioritise, and encourage strong action towards the transition to the circular economy.

5.2.2 LL orientation towards policies and regulations

Business Model Innovation is an iterative journey that involves experimentation, piloting, gaining experience, and ultimately scaling up solutions (Bocken et al., 2019). The process of transforming or creating new circular business models (CBMs) is referred to as **CBM innovation (CBMI)** and it is a strategic process that specifically focuses on conceptualizing and implementing CBMs (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020).

In the B-WaterSmart project, after conducting a review in WP4 (Circular economy value chains) on the proposed circular solutions (with an implementation-focus) and CBMs in the LL's of the B-WaterSmart project, two distinct contexts of Living Labs (LLs) have been observed characterized by their issues and the relationship of their actions with respect to the policies and regulations affecting to these. On the one side, LLs like Lisbon and East Frisia face direct impacts from restrictive regulatory barriers on the proposed circular solutions (i.e. urban water reuse and industrial water reuse in dairy industry). On the other side, LLs like Alicante (Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion), Venice (increase of industrial reuse), Flanders (stormwater reuse for subirrigation), and Bodø (Increase of energy production through biogas) have a lesser impact by policies and regulations where proposed circular solutions may be limited but not restricted by current regulations.

Given the competencies and capabilities required to overcome strict regulation barriers, LLs affected by these, will tend to be driven by public authorities, while LLs not affected by strict regulations will be generally led by water companies. This differentiation is general in nature and does not necessarily imply that water companies, especially those of a public nature (e.g. East Frisia), lack the capacities and competencies to manage strict regulatory barriers. However, the origin of their actions will have a differentiated character with respect to public authorities and will require the establishment of a channel

with public bodies and regulators to overcome obstacles in achieving circular implementation in their processes.

The objective of public authorities is to create social and environmental beneficial impacts to citizens, industrial sectors, and the different communities comprising society. For this reason, their efforts within the LL will be directed towards promoting social and environmental changes through increasing awareness, driving favourable policies and regulations, fostering collaboration between sectors, promoting research, all in all enabling a framework that can promote the development of these solutions and the implementation of circular solutions through successful CBM. Since their focus prioritizes environmental and social aspects, over economic ones, they generally depend on public funding sources to sustain their operational activities and ensure the economic and financial viability of CBMs.

The primary goal of a water company is to ensure water service; therefore, their competencies will be more aligned with technological innovation, and they will be more limited in driving social innovation (referring to the policy and regulations aspects). However, the advantages of LLs led by these entities are that they will develop techno-economic evidence through technology experimentation and detailed impact analysis, providing reliable data for the assessment of CBMs. On the other hand, they will have the ability to identify economic, operational, organizational, and regulatory barriers and drivers related to circular solutions under the existing or developing regulatory framework. These micro and meso level assessments will serve as input for regulators to obtain feedback on existing policies and develop efficient policy instruments specifically targeted at existing issues.

LLs led by public authorities, with the aim of enabling circular solution implementation, generally will address issues from a more macro and less specific context. On the other hand, LLs led by water utilities, through the detection and evaluation of the impacts of policy and regulation P&R, will have greater impact on innovation at a more micro-level of application. Both contexts are not mutually exclusive and should be balanced (presence of both in the LL), with the participation of regulators, and involving public institutions, to obtain feedback from water utilities in the case of LLs led by water utilities; and on the other hand, the participation of water utilities in the development of P&R proposals to overcome barriers. The ideal scenario is that LLs are structured in such a way that all parties are involved, regardless of whether it is guided by one agent or another. This allows for the engagement of all stakeholders in the process.

5.2.3 Circular Business Models Innovation stages and dependence on policies and regulations.

The Circular Business Models Innovation (CBMI) in a LL can be described as following the next phases: Framing and Scoping, Ideation, Detail Design, and Implementation. Starting from the conception and goal-setting phase of the LL (Framing and Scoping stages), through the Ideation stage (consisting in a generation, selection of ideas and development of a CBM concept phase), the detailed design stage (consisting in a experimentation, prioritization of CBMs, detailed design, and piloting phase), to finally the development of the implementation plan, the impacts of P&R must be taken into account. The main reason is that P&R introduces a bias in the selection of ideas, solutions and subsequently CBMs.

Concurrently during the CBMI, the impacts of P&R that were not initially identified will be clarified in more detail, thus detecting new barriers or opportunities (e.g., when projects are lengthy and new

regulations come into effect favouring certain solutions). This will allow for the analysis, evaluation, and reworking of policies to make them more adapted and supportive of the implementation of CBMs in the LLs.

Next, it is described how P&R affect each stage of the CBMI process and how this process can provide feedback for the adaptation and creation of new P&R:

- Framing and scoping stage

LLs that have a direct impact on P&R (enabling LLs) and their direct objective is the modification, adaptation, or design of new P&R must consider in this phase the scope of these objectives and their impact on the solutions proposed.

Regardless, all LLs will be impacted by P&R affecting proposed solutions and CBMs to varying degrees. LLs will initially identify these impacts by analysing barriers and drivers. These impacts influence issue selection, with existing regulations often leading to prioritization of certain issues. Environments with fewer restrictions tend to prioritize actions, narrowing the LL's scope. Conversely, detection of favourable policies biases LL's scope towards issues supported by more favourable policies.

- Ideation stage

In the ideation phase, proposals for solutions to the problems identified in the previous phase are generated. Preliminary assessments are also conducted to select the most viable ideas. It is at this point where P&R can influence the selection or rejection of ideas, introducing a bias based on the intensity of the impacts of these P&R. It is essential that, if a promising idea is ultimately rejected due to regulatory reasons, this issue is documented and communicated to the authorities. This is crucial because it could be a case of an untapped potential due to lack of awareness. Before definitively rejecting an idea and to avoid potential premature selection bias, an analysis should be conducted to determine if the impact is solvable within a timeframe suitable for implementing the idea. Consequently, this will impact the selection of the business model during the development of the concept and its preliminary design, especially regarding financing mechanisms and potential revenue sources (e.g., regulatory restrictions on the commercialization of certain by-products, waste categorization, etc.).

- Detail design stage

This stage involves of experimentation, detailed design, and piloting. It is a crucial stage for the development of the CBM and requires a deeper analysis of the legal aspects underlying the solutions. While previous phases generally consider P&R from a broader perspective, these stages identify the practical impacts of the P&R framework when applied in real settings.

In the experimentation phase, environmental regulations and quality standards affecting the design of CBM products and services are considered for testing.

During the prioritization phase, there is a bias in selecting solutions and associated CBMs toward those with less regulatory impact or more favorable policies.

In the detailed design phase, experimentation results are incorporated, and CBMs are refined based on detailed analyses that aim to address specific uncertainties that need to be minimized.

This refinement process also considers the level of analysis from preliminary feasibility studies conducted in earlier stages.

This phase yields two main feedback loops: implementers analyze P&R impacts on final cost structure, revenue streams, financing instruments, organizational structure, operational processes, risk assessments, and administrative efforts. Regulators observe and analyze current regulation impacts. Incorporating feedback from both implementers and regulators is crucial for optimizing processes, minimizing risks, and planning CBM implementation. This collaborative effort also facilitates information collection, which aids regulators in adapting P&R based on the input from both feedback loops.

During the Pilot Testing Phase, significant impacts stem from P&R. Obtaining permits and meeting necessary requirements for tests can be particularly challenging due to regulatory constraints, leading to potential delays. It is crucial to document and communicate critical factors such as these. This phase involves navigating complex operational processes and bureaucratic procedures, including securing permits and licenses for pilots. Implementers and regulators must carefully assess existing regulatory issues and their real-world application to ensure compliance with regulatory standards. As for the detail design phase, significant feedback loops from both implementers and regulators can be gathered for the adaptation and creation of new P&R.

- Implementation stage

This phase focuses on the practical execution of all plans designed during the previous stages. All risks associated with regulation and its potential evolution should have been detected and considered in earlier phases. Regarding P&R aspects, compliance with existing regulations must occur before implementation, adhering to all permits and licenses necessary to launch the circular business model. Likewise, a plan for periodic monitoring and follow-up of regulations and policies should be established to stay updated on changes related to regulation and adapt and adjust CBMs with minimal impact. To achieve this, it is advisable to maintain communication channels regarding regulatory impacts with the relevant authorities.

Conclusions:

From a LL perspective, it has been observed that we deal with two starting orientations in LLs which will affect CBM innovation: one motivated and oriented from the outset to promote P&R changes (enabling), and another that does not have that function as its end goal. LLs oriented from the outset to encourage changes in P&R tend to work on the more visible aspects of P&R, and their natural sphere of influence is at the macro level (Figure 5) although this doesn't mean that the operational part of the selected solutions won't also address aspects at the meso and micro levels.

On the other hand, all solutions are affected by P&R, and therefore all LLs, when acting at the micro level during the development of solutions, will serve as perfect detectors in their normal activity to assess the real influence of P&R on innovation activity. It has also been observed that, in many cases, regulators are not aware of the real impact of P&R applied at the micro level, and it is challenging to detect them from the macro level at which they operate.

Figure 5. Feedback loop of P&R

The discussion has addressed how, both in establishing the initial objectives of LLs and in the CBMI, multiple filters are applied when selecting goals, problems, solutions, and CBMs based on P&R aspects, and how these biases selections in the best-case scenario or hinder their development in the worst. It is important to note that this information often has internal use and is not usually collected in a structured manner, resulting in its loss.

As a best practice throughout the design of a CBM, it is important that LLs systematically collect such information for analysis and treatment. This will enable the regulator to promote an optimal innovation environment, allowing the best ideas to be carried forward and facilitating the growth of novel and high-impact solutions.

Thus, P&R affect many more aspects than those that can be detected initially, and communication between regulators (macro) and the organization implementing solutions (micro) is crucial to identifying regulatory aspects that may be influencing their decision-making. Therefore, from the regulators' perspective, it is necessary to build a channel that generates a real flow of information so that innovation environments can report all aspects related to P&R that are conditioning the evolution of their project.

5.3 Mapping policy and regulation instruments, issues and strengths at EU and LL level

This section presents a mapping of the policy and regulation instruments, addressing water-related circularity, relevant for recommendations and with focus on the B-WaterSmart resources identified in chapter 3. Additionally, it identifies the issues and strengths to achieve water-related circularity. A compilation of different sources of information were considered, namely contributions from B-WaterSmart developments, as from the InAll partners developing the strategic planning process (Cardoso et al., 2022), D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023), strategic agendas of the LLs (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023), the interactive session on Policy & Regulation (section 4.3 and Annex 2), Lisbon LL meeting on Policy & Regulation focused on water reuse and related-issues (section 4.4). Additional contributions were included by the authors, according to the project's description of work, based on their expertise, as presented in section 4.1.

5.3.1 Digitalisation and IoT

Table 5 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as issues and strengths concerning digitalisation and IoT.

Table 5. Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in digitalisation and IoT

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive (EU) 2022/2555 - NIS2 Directive on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union • Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on General Data Protection (GDPR) • Digital Decade policy programme 2030 • EU Artificial Intelligence Act (proposal agreed)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(-) Data confidentiality and security, with implication to data collection from smart meters</p> <p>Source: Interactive session on P&R</p> <p>(-) Lack of open data</p> <p>(-) Lack of investment in the institutions (cost of collecting data)</p> <p>(-) Low perception of the value of collecting and sharing data</p> <p>(-) Need to identify data essential for policy and regulation or other purposes</p>
Alicante, Spain
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on the Protection of Personal Data and the guarantee of digital rights
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>(+) Technical and organizational Security measures against unauthorized access.</p> <p>(-) Lack of clear guidelines on how personal data should be collected and processed in this specific context.</p> <p>(-) Lack of updates addressing the current technological challenges and solutions.</p> <p>(-) Lack of compliance control of the law in this specific context.</p>
East Frisia, Germany
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG) • NIS2 • KRITIS • IT security standard water/wastewater (B3S) • Supervisory authorities of the federal states
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022)</p>

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
<p>assessed regarding the application of tools # 22, #23, and #28. Therefore, case-specific, and not general aspects and strengths of policies and laws are listed</p> <p>(+) Political ambitions to increase the level of digitalization in Germany</p> <p>(-) Multiple regulations for digital solutions</p> <p>(-) Data confidentiality: Citizens' data protection concerns regarding the collection and analysis of personal and household data</p> <p>(-) Interoperability of data must be guaranteed</p>
Lisbon, Portugal
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Data Protection Law, Law n.º 58/2019, of 8 August • Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority (ERSAR) quality of service assessment Security and Resilience Index (Cardoso et al., 2021)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas</p> <p>(-) Data confidentiality, with implication to data collection from smart meters for all types of water</p> <p>Source: InAll, Cardoso et al. (2021, 2023); Silva et al. (2022)</p> <p>(+) ERSAR's Security and Resilience Index addresses cybersecurity i) governance & operationalization, ii) risk management, iii) communication, iv) planning</p>

5.3.2 Drinking water

Table 6 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as issues and strengths concerning drinking water.

Table 6. Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in drinking water

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive 2000/60/EC. Water framework directive (WFD) • Directive (EU) 2020/2184. Drinking Water Directive (DWD) • Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on General Data Protection (GDPR) • Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs • Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: Interactive session on P&R</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) DWD establishes water leakage level should be assessed by all Member States and reduced if they are above a certain threshold (-) Need to protect drinking water quality from micropollutants or unknown substances in the water sources (-) Need to ensure drinking water quality at point of consumption via network monitoring (-) Need to allocate fit-for-purpose water quality (e.g., avoid using drinking water for non-potable uses) (-) lack of investments to renew drinking water supply network
Bodø, Norway
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR (data protection)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) High need for better overview of leakages in municipalities in Norway (-) Data confidentiality, with implication to data collection from smart meters (-) Water meters are not mandatory in some municipalities (high costs) <p>Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) Bodø Municipality is testing out new ways to engage citizens, e.g. by organising a Circularity Week in the autumn of 2023 (+) Independent authorities, e.g. the Office of the Auditor General of Norway recently reviewed the Government's efforts to provide safe drinking water and criticised the current effort to reduce leakages and renew water infrastructure (+) Monitoring and evaluation carried out through the Norwegian Environment Agency, and reported in relation to the SDGs and every 4 years to the UN Climate Convention
East Frisia, Germany
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinking Water Ordinance • Food Hygiene Regulation (LMHV) • Federal Water Act (AVBWasserV) • Surface Water Ordinance • Ground Water Ordinance • Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG) • Local and Regional water authorities
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022)</p> <p>assessed regarding the application of tools # 22, #23, and #28.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (-) Measures identified on the basis of the digital tools must take into account the requirements of water quality, water treatment, water abstraction, water supplier obligations and monitoring requirements under the EU Directive and national legislation (-) Digitalisation is a major but still emerging topic and a diverse set of regulations apply for digital solutions in the water sector, e.g. data protection, data security

5.3.3 Energy

Table 7 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as issues and strengths concerning energy.

Table 7 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in energy

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Green Deal • COM(2020) on Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) • EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (i.e. "green taxonomy") • European Circular Economy Monitoring Framework • Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on use of energy from renewable sources • COM(2022) on urban wastewater treatment (recast) • Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste • European Funds for Regional Development 2021-2027
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(+) Energy recovery for self-consumption to cope with the WWTPs' high energy demand towards energy neutrality</p> <p>(-) Lack of EU policy for climate efficiency in households, buildings, and neighbourhoods</p>
Alicante, Spain
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spanish Circular Economy Strategy • National Biogas Roadmap • Regional Biogas Roadmap • Long-Term Decarbonization Strategy (ELP 2050) • National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) • Law 7/2022 on waste and contaminated soil for a circular economy • Law 29/2021, adopting urgent measures in the energy sector to promote electric mobility, self-consumption, and the deployment of renewable energies • Law 7/2021 of 20 May on climate change and energy transition • Renewable Energy Plan (PER) 2011-2020
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(+) Energy recovery for self-consumption and high energy requirement of WWTPs</p> <p>(+) Several potential waste producers for biogas production</p> <p>(+) Promotion of biogas, biomethane, and renewable hydrogen</p> <p>(-) Cost of waste transport</p> <p>(-) Requirement of legal certification for solid waste management</p> <p>(-) Lack of policies and regulations related to new type of renewable energies</p> <p>(-) Civil works for installing energy production only feasible for large WWTPs</p>

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
Bodø, Norway
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Strategy for the Circular Economy (2021) • Regulation on the limitation of pollution (Pollution Regulation), FOR-2004-06-01-931, Department of Climate and Environment • Statal planning guideline for climate and energy planning and climate adaptation • Enova, Norwegian state enterprise promoting the development and upscaling of sustainable energy and climate technology
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(+) Both Iris and Bodø kommune have expressed interest in the installation of a biogas generator for the Salten region.</p> <p>(-) Regulation on handling digestate products</p> <p>Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)</p> <p>(+) Enough competencies and knowledge</p> <p>(+) Availability of data & information</p> <p>(+) Financing support for establishment of biogas production facilities</p> <p>(+) Bodø Municipality is testing out new ways to engage citizens, e.g. by organising a Circularity Week in the autumn of 2023</p> <p>(+) Monitoring and evaluation carried out through the Norwegian Environment Agency, and reported in relation to the SDGs and every 4 years to the UN Climate Convention</p> <p>(+) Collaboration with others in the Salten Region. Iris Salten already established an intermunicipal waste management company serving the whole region</p> <p>(-) Need to consider synergies and benefits across municipalities when planning/selecting solutions</p> <p>(-) Need to finalize revision of the national regulation on organic fertilizers. Uncertainty concerning the organic fertilizer regulation has consequences on biogas production</p>
Lisbon, Portugal
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <p>-</p>
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(-) Lack of national policy for climate efficiency in households, building and neighbourhoods</p>
Venice, Italy
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Adaptation Strategy (NAS; Directorial Decree n. 86 of 16 June 2015) • National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) • Regulation of the water sector and incentives (ARERA) • Plan for Circular Economy in 2017 • Programs towards greenhouse gases emission reduction and climate change mitigation (C40 Cities, 2022)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(+) Increasingly defined plans and incentives for energy recovery in the water sector (ARERA)</p>

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

- (-) Not clearly defined National/Regional regulatory framework to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste
- (-) Complexity of the national regulatory system

5.3.4 Nutrients, biosolids and others

Table 8 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as issues and strengths concerning nutrients, biosolids, and others.

Table 8 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in nutrients, biosolids, and others

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
Policies and regulation

- Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products
- European Funds for Regional Development 2021-2027
- The EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (i.e. "green taxonomy")
- European Circular Economy Monitoring Framework
- Directive 2008/98/EC on waste
- Council Directive 86/278/EEC on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)

(-) Lack of a consensus at European level to promote a common roadmap for sludge management

Source: Interactive session on P&R

(-) Product (value issues): lack of comprehensive strategic plans for nutrient management (in case of sludge valorisation in agriculture); lack of characterization/standardization of byproducts.

(-) Market (revenue issues): lack of market penetration and incentives, lack of legislation to promote nutrient recovery and reuse markets, low market acceptance of nutrients/products recovered from wastewater (e.g. compost), need to focus on other upcycling alternatives for nitrogen besides fertilization (e.g., protein production for animal feed)

(-) Transaction (buyers and sellers' issues): need to promote a generational change towards an increased market acceptance of nutrients and biosolids reuse, need to change the semantics related with nutrients and biosolids reuse (focus on "recovering", not on "treatment")

Alicante, Spain
Policies and regulation

- **Spanish Circular Economy Strategy**
- Law 47/2022, on the production of water against diffuse pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources
- Royal Decree 1310/1990, of 29 October, regulating the use in agriculture of sludge from treatment
- Orden AAA/1072/2013, of 7 June, on the use in agriculture of sludge from treatment

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
<p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) Shortage of ammonia-based products (+) Rising ammonia prices (+) Several potential consumers of the recovered product (-) Cost of product transport (-) High cost of equipment (-) Competitive market <p>Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (-) Inadequate regulatory framework for sludge management and valorisation leading to a lack of funding for new investments (-) Great regulatory uncertainty and heterogeneity of criteria at territorial level (-) Missing review and updating of the regulations related to sludge management, taking into account technological developments, international best practices, and environmental sustainability objectives
Venice, Italy
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan for Circular Economy in 2017 • National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) • Regulation of the water sector and incentives (ARERA) • DGRV n. 2241/2005 and DGRV n. 1407/2006 – regional regulation about quality assurance of sludge finalized to agricultural application • Legislative Decree N. 99/92 national regulation on sludge application in agriculture and Legislative Decree N. 109/2018 with revision of parameters and limit to be respected for sludge application in agriculture • Legislative Decree n. 152/2006, Part IV - Article 184 ter, about recovery products classification within the End of Waste criteria (Waste Framework Directive, 2008/98/EC) • Regional Decree n. 120/2018 technical requirements for the End of Waste “case by case” evaluation. • Legislative Decree N. 75/2010 national regulation on fertilizers and soil amendments (also derived from recovery products)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (-) Complexity of the national regulatory system (-) Not clearly defined National/Regional regulatory framework to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste (-) Not enough interlinkage between water and waste policy to make sustainable products recovery and reuse (“end of waste classification” delegated to the arbitrary “case by case” evaluation, that in the Venice LL can impact N-salt valorisation) <p>Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) General roles are clear (-) Need to clarify and define regulation to be adopted to the management/delivery of salts produced, for N-recovery by stripping strategy (-) Issues about shared knowledge and coordination of policy, need of a decision support system at regional scale (-) Scattered data to support the implementation and management

5.3.5 Reclaimed water

Table 9 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as

issues and strengths concerning reclaimed water.

Table 9 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in water reuse

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COM(2015)614 on Circular Economy Action Plan • European Funds for Regional Development 2021-2027 • Directive 91/271/EEC, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) • Directive 2000/60/EC, the Water framework directive (WFD) • Directive (EU) 2020/2184, the Drinking Water Directive (DWD) • COM(2022)541 final, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive recast • The EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (i.e. "green taxonomy") • European Circular Economy Monitoring Framework • Regulation (EC) No 852/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs • Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products • Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse (on agricultural irrigation)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (-) Missing EU agenda on water reuse (non-potable water reuse, IPR, DPR) (-) Missing EU regulation and legislation on indirect and direct potable reuse (IPR, DPR) (-) Missing EU regulation and legislation for non-potable reclaimed water for irrigation, urban and industrial uses, and for potable uses (-) Missing EU regulation and legislation to improve risk assessment process (-) Missing EU policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication (-) Lack of a EU regulatory framework that facilitates the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste <p>Source: Interactive session on P&R</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) Multiple users improve technical (e.g., decrease demand peaks) and economic feasibility of water reuse (-) Business and funding issues (-) Water reuse requires dedicated distribution network (who to build and operate this new network?) (-) Missing guidelines for the water reuse licensing process by the water authorities (-) Perception of worse water quality for irrigation (-) Unclear how extensive risk assessment for agricultural use should be (-) Need to address (define and report) indirect reuse <p>Source: EU news (Euractiv.com)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) ReWaterEU – proposal of a new initiative intending to help reduce the EU vulnerability to the effects of climate change on water resources by guaranteeing access to water for public supply in terms of quantity and quality at fair prices, as well as the availability of water for agriculture, tourism and industrial uses, and the protection of different ecosystems. The plan is to be financed by EU funds and private investment. (+) The European Commission is planning to launch, in March 2024, a Water Resilience Initiative, which will include a series of immediate actions and launch a public debate on achieving water resilience.
Alicante, Spain
<p>Policies and regulation</p>

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

- Ley de Aguas, 1985
- Royal Legislative Decree 2001 (revised Water Act); Royal Decree 1620/2007, a series of measures were introduced to establish the legal regime for the reuse of treated wastewater
- Spanish Circular Economy Strategy 2030 Project Alicante Agua Circular
- Art. 272-273 of the RDPH (Reglamento del Dominio Público Hidráulico) main regulation applicable to water reuse

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)

(+) Water reuse provides support to the implementation of other technologies

(-) Complexity in decision making in circular economy

(-) Complexity in the justification to the (public) administrations for the investment on water reuse

(-) Difficulty to model some elements in a simple way

(-) Business model underdevelopment

Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)

(-) The value chain of reclaimed water and roles and responsibilities are not well defined. Overlap and sometimes lack of involvement of the parties

(-) Lack of policy coherence with regard to the water allocated by a concession or a legitimate title for the private use of water, as it is sometimes not used by its holder

(-) Rigidity in administrative concessions can create challenges for certain users, especially in situations where adjustments or adaptations are required due to changes in hydrological conditions or specific user needs

East Frisia, Germany
Policies and regulation

- National Water Strategy
- Food Hygiene Regulation (LMHV)
- Drinking Water Ordinance
- Federal Water Act
- Surface Water Ordinance
- Ground Water Ordinance
- Local and Regional water authorities
- Environmental Information Act

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>evaluated regarding the usage of treated cow water in the food production. Therefore, case-specific, and not general issues and strengths of policies and legislations are listed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (-) Water reuse is a new topic, so there is a gap in policy and regulation for reuse of recycled water in different areas (e.g. industrial sector) (-) Responsibility for water reuse in dairy industry is spread across different authorities, which complicates decision-making. Therefore, it needs political empowerment of authorities to also consider the contribution of re-use approaches to overarching environmental policy objectives in the approval process (-) Not enough investment support and the refinancing of high opex and capex (+) Relevant authorities for LL East Frisia are open to an experience exchange across the federal state borders with other authorities in whose areas such reuse has or will be approved (+) Public interest and support for resource-saving reuse solutions (+) Recently issued national water strategy is a good starting point for the implementation of reuse measures. The national strategy needs to be complemented by a federal state water strategy that can promote industrial reuse at the level where the actual decisions are taken (+) Integrity and transparency practices across water policies, water institutions and water governance frameworks for greater accountability and trust in decision-making
Flanders, Belgium
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <p>-</p>
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (+) Dashboards information-sharing platforms are in place (-) Need to align federal and regional risk assessment procedures. Disparities in risk assessment for water reuse as environment and water are regulated at the regional level, health is regulated at a federal level (-) Need to improve access to and coherence among different data platforms and stimulate cross-border data sharing (-) Return on investment for water-related innovations is low, causing heavy reliance on public funding (-) Need of a broader involvement of stakeholders in the value chain and in upstream and downstream areas could improve shared problem ownership and investment opportunities
Lisbon, Portugal
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decree Law 119/2019, of 21 August, establishing the legal regime for producing reclaimed water, obtained from wastewater treatment – (all non-potable uses) reclaimed water production licence and utilisation licence issued by ARH Tagus • Decree Law 16/2021, of 24 February, clarifying reclaimed water production is part of the wastewater service and a new activity committed to multi-municipal wastewater systems • Decree Law 11/2023, of 10 February, reforms and simplifies environmental licensing • Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority (ERSAR) quality of service assessment Reclaimed water production indicator with reference values depending on WEI+ (Cardoso et al., 2021) • Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority (ERSAR) guidelines for financing water reuse • PENSAARP2030 – Portuguese strategic plan for the decade, for water, wastewater, and stormwater services • PERAL – Lisbon water reuse strategic plan • PNA – National Water Plan

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

- PNUEA – National Plan for Efficient Water Use

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)

(+) National strategic plan for the decade, for all water services (drinking water, urban wastewater, and stormwater) and addressing water circularity

(+) Regulation of the water and wastewater services, including quality of service assessment and guidelines for financing the services

(+) Pioneer national legislation on water reuse, covering all non-potable uses and based on ISO standards

(+) Local (Lisbon) political awareness and willingness to reuse water and a strategic plan for the municipality

(-) Unclear legal framework regarding the existence of water supply utilities in Lisbon other than EPAL

(-) Current legislation does not allow selling/transferring reclaimed water to third parties to increase water reuse potential and viability (no secondary users allowed)

(-) National legislation after the new UWWTD will be needed

Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)

(-) Need for planning and action at local and basin levels. Drought issues should be dealt in advance by incorporating the principles and good practices in the use of water in non-potable uses in the city, evolving from the current situation

(-) Outdated regulations on building water systems are a barrier to the licensing of rainwater harvesting and water reuse systems

(-) Lack of knowledge and information on reclaimed water quality evolution in the distribution network

(-) Lack of public awareness of the local context that may increase water scarcity in Lisbon

(-) Lack of collaboration with stakeholders and potential users focusing on the benefits of using reclaimed water in fit-for-purpose uses

(-) Need to improve a common ground of knowledge on quantity and quality aspects, for reaching consensus with the authorities and involved stakeholders, and engagement with the users (urban, rural, or industrial) of reclaimed water

(-) Need for adjusting the legal framework of the water distribution service in Lisbon, as new water types (e.g. reclaimed water) should be delivered via a public distribution network

Source: euroactiv.com

(+) ReWaterEU plan with regard to the management of water resources, the Portuguese government proposes to implement measures such as reducing water losses in distribution systems, optimising storage, and transport infrastructures, reusing water for non-potable purposes in the urban, tourist, industrial, and agricultural sectors, and investing in desalination plants.

Source: Lisbon LL meeting on P&R (section 4.4)

Is it necessary to legislate or regulate at European, national, or local level?

Q1. Other (than agricultural irrigation) reclaimed water uses

- At EU level, a future revision of the Regulation (EU) 2020/741, should consider the establishment of minimum requirements for other uses than agricultural irrigation, namely industrial and urban uses.
- In Portugal, these uses are already legislated, for example for air conditioning in buildings, dust production control on construction sites (industrial) and urban irrigation, street cleaning, vehicle, and municipal waste bins cleaning.

Q2 & Q3 & Q4.

Indirect water reuse & Emission Limit Values vs. capacity of receiving body and intended uses (different permit types) &

Aquifer recharge

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

- Current lack of a uniform position among the EU countries regarding the accounting of indirect water reuse, e.g., in Spain it is, whether in Portugal it is not - only licensed water reuse (e.g. direct reuse) is accounted for.
- ERSAR recommendation for water reuse financing is based on the “user pays” principle, meaning the additional treatment for reuse should be paid by the water user and not charged to the wastewater service.
- Environmental uses (i.e., support of wetlands and supplementation of stream, river, and lake flows, without contact with the human body) used to be considered as water reuse in the Portuguese legislation and are no longer considered.
- If WWTP discharges have a significant impact on water quality in a water body that is used for water abstraction (e.g., irrigation or industry) there are no clear boundaries between discharge and (indirect) reuse. The downstream water abstraction permit should take into account if the flow for the ecosystem maintenance is safeguarded and if the treated wastewater quality (discharge permit) after dilution in the water body fits the intended purpose. If additional treatment is needed, according to ERSARs’ recommendation, the additional cost should be charged to the water abstraction permit owner.
- Currently, there is not a uniform position among the EU countries regarding the aquifer recharge as water reuse. In Portugal, the legislation does not consider it, but in the 2024 State budget includes funding for a pilot project on managed aquifer recharge for a sound assessment of the environmental impact of this potential complementary solution for tackling water scarcity.

Q5. Evolution in minimum quality requirements and monitoring

- The fit-for-purpose principle should be maintained.
- Increased quality requirements for treated wastewater discharge to be introduced by the recast of the Urban Wastewater Directive can make water reuse easier (closer and not necessarily higher water quality requirements for reuse and lower additional/advanced treatment needed for reclamation).
- How to cope with monitoring results affected by external sources of contamination resulting from non-authorized uses of the space (e.g., irrigation in urban gardens or parks used for camping by homeless people). Monitoring is relevant but must not represent a big share of the direct costs of water reuse.
- Monitoring effort is expected to be higher initially (validation period) and then to decrease upon data records of water quality reliability. Simpler and cost-effective, ideally on-line, monitoring of proxy/screening indicators of water quality.

Q6. Prioritize reclaimed water uses in licensing

- The prioritization of water reuse should be decided according to the local environmental, technical, economic, and social circumstances.
- Reclaimed water should be clearly integrated in local/regional water balance. There will be no investment in reuse if there is no security of supply continuity.

Q7. Allow distribution/sale of reclaimed water to third parties, by licensed users &

Q8. Autonomize/regulate the reclaimed water supply service &

Q9. Evolution of economic regulation &

- In Portugal, current legislation does not allow a licensed reclaimed water user to pass on the reclaimed water to third parties due to risk management concerns. This is a major barrier to the implementation of water reuse in urban areas. The creation and regulation/licensing of a reclaimed water supply service could overcome this bottleneck through a producer- distributor-user(s) model, each party with an adequate risk management. Multiple users likely offer a steadier consumption with the inherent technical and financial advantages.

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

- In Portugal, reclaimed water production and/or distribution can be included in the activity of a water utility, with a proper adjustment of the concession contract. It should be noted that the financial model for economic viability of reclaimed water supply is much more complex than for drinking water supply (variation in demand throughout the year and among years, and fewer interested parties).
- The 'cost-recovery principle' established at EU level and the 'user pays' principle recommended in Portugal may impair the affordability/willingness-to-pay for water reuse vs. freshwater abstraction, unless water scarcity is reflected on the freshwater costs and/or the wastewater treatment for discharge, supported by the respective tariff, gets closer to the water reclamation requirements, as expected through the UWWTD recast.
- Water reuse often secures freshwater availability for other purposes, including drinking water production, agriculture irrigation, so the financial model should assess a fair share of water reuse costs, particularly investment, across water services and freshwater abstraction.

Q10. Relevance of the existence of strategic planning

Strategic planning for water reuse, integrated in a broader regional water balance, is essential and should involve all key stakeholders and economic activities, and consider all existing sources, including reclaimed water.

Venice, Italy

Policies and regulation

- National Adaptation Strategy (NAS; Directorial Decree n. 86 of 16th June 2015)
- Plan for Circular Economy in 2017
- Water Safeguard Plan Veneto region
- Regional Plan for the lagoon protection (Regional Masterplan 2000)
- Ministerial Decree n. 185/2003 national regulation on water reuse for agricultural, urban, and industrial purposes
- Law 68/2023 -Decree Law 39/2023 Urgent provisions for contrasting water scarcity (referring to EU Regulation 2020/741 for water agricultural reuse)
- National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)
- Regulation of the water sector and incentives (ARERA)
- Legislative Decree n. 152/2006 Part III - about protection of surface, marine and groundwater against pollution
- Ministerial Decree of 30 July 1999 (from "Ronchi-Costa" Decree) for the quality protection of the Venice lagoon

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)

- (-) Lack of a national water reuse strategy
- (-) Not clearly defined national/regional regulatory framework to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste
- (-) Complexity of the national regulatory system

Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)

- (-) For the agricultural water reuse there are ambiguities on roles/responsibilities distribution among the water reuse chain
- (-) Lack of data to support the implementation and management

5.3.6 Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses

Table 10 presents the policy and regulation instruments relevant for recommendations, as well as issues and strengths concerning stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses.

Table 10 Policy and regulation instruments, issues, and strengths in stormwater

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)
European
<p>Policies and regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources • Directive 2000/60/EC, the Water framework directive (WFD) • Directive 2007/60/EC, on the assessment and management of flood risks • Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse (on agricultural irrigation)
<p>Issues (-) and Strengths (+)</p> <p>Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)</p> <p>(-) Lack of international agreements on transboundary water flow (across borders), particularly for the Southwest region, where inflow of surface water is important</p> <p>Source: Interactive session on P&R</p> <p>(+) Opportunity to use nature-based solutions to manage stormwater quantity and quality</p> <p>(-) Need to improve governance (define roles, responsibility, and ownership)</p> <p>(-) Who and how to pay for an unstable source as stormwater</p> <p>(-) Need to promote storage and use of rain/stormwater in rural and urban (including households) spaces</p> <p>(-) Need to involve stakeholders in heavy rain/stormwater management as a shared challenge</p>
Flanders, Belgium
<p>Source: Vlakwa</p> <p>Stormwater collection in Flanders is a municipal competence. In practice, most municipalities outsource this to intermunicipal companies or Aquafin. There is not yet a specific legal framework for agriculture irrigation water in Flanders. Depending on how rainwater is collected and stored, it can be considered groundwater, surface water or rainwater. In the first two cases regulations (and fees) might apply (see section below on rainwater reuse). Wastewater collection, including rainwater (stormwater) collection is regulated at two geographic levels: i) Wastewater collection and rainwater collection at the municipal level is a municipal competence. Many municipalities have appointed another party as responsible for sewage water collection, often an intermunicipal company (intercommunale), or in some Aquafin NV (see below); ii) Aquafin NV is responsible for the supra-municipal treatment (and transport) of wastewater in Flanders. Most municipal WWTPs are owned and operated by Aquafin.</p> <p>Flemish municipalities are encouraged to make a Rainwater and Drought Plan (HWDP). Municipalities that do not have such a plan by 2024 will not have access to water-related subsidies. A HWDP contains a long-term vision on rainwater infrastructure and source measures to retain rainwater, reuse it, and infiltrate it. In more detail: i) the HWDP outlines the future system, in which rainwater will be separately collected. This is in contrast with the current systems, where often (not always) rainwater and household discharge are collected together in a combined system; ii) HWDPs indicate where water should be buffered and where it can be infiltrated, in order to prevent rainwater flooding and to recharge the phreatic aquifer where possible; iii) the HWDPs seek to avoid that future investment will require separate plans, by making sure a municipality-wide standardized plan is available. In many cases, the waste hierarchy model ('Lansink's Ladder') is applied for prioritization: reuse – infiltration – buffering.</p>

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

In practice, HWDPs are developed by external consultants or by the intermunicipal company that is responsible for wastewater in the municipality. B-WaterSmart's partner Aquafin takes up this role for some municipalities in Flanders.

Newly built houses and other buildings are subject to regulations concerning the collection of rainwater (Vlaamse Regering n.d.(a)): i) a rainwater well is mandatory, with volumes depending on the roof surface; ii) an infiltration facility is mandatory, in some cases at a collective level; iii) municipalities and provinces can impose more stringent rules than those at the regional (Flemish level).

The Flemish Government approved the regional Rainwater Ordinance 2023 on February 2023 (RWO, 2023). It defines that: (for new constructions or large renovations) rainwater must be collected separately from (urban) wastewater; the (minimal) size of rainwater wells; the infiltration of the overflow water; and the obliged installation of a rainwater-piping network in houses (Vlaamse Regering, 2022). The feedback procedure can be followed online (for the SERV and Minaraad feedback, see SERV 2022).

In Flanders there is regulation on use of the different water sources for irrigation: i) depending on volumes, there is a notification duty or a permit requirement for groundwater use, which includes charges (Vlaamse Regering, n.d.(b)); ii) depending on volumes, there is a notification duty or a permit requirement for water capture from surface water bodies (Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij n.d.(a)). The exact regulation depends on the type of water course and which authority is responsible for the course.

During periods of drought, the provincial governor can impose a temporary ban on the capture of water from surface water bodies. Over the last few years dry summers have seen such bans for most of the territory, and for some regions bans were in place all year round.

Collected rainwater that is transported through a ditch to a buffer basin might fall under the regulations of surface water bodies. An online tool, the "Vlaamse Hydrografische Atlas", maps all official surface water bodies and describes which authority is responsible. It allows actors to check whether the water body is considered as a surface water body (Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij n.d.(b)).

Water bodies that are not surface water bodies but are connected to the groundwater fall under the groundwater regulations (Inagro 2023). This includes, for example, 'open' rainwater basins that are not separated from the groundwater by e.g. a lay of clay or plastic foil. Water bodies that are isolated from groundwater do not fall under this regulation.

If rainwater is to be stored underground before reuse, it should follow the regulations in Vlarem 5.54 ("het kunstmatig aanvullen van grondwater"; Vlaamse Regering 1995). Infiltration of non-polluted rainwater including the use for irrigation is example from these regulations (Vlarem II Bijlage, Rubriek 54, Sectie 54.2).

Policies and regulation

- National adaptation strategy
- National adaptation plans at the national and regional levels. Flemish Climate Policy Plan (VKP) 2013-2020. Flemish Mitigation Plan (VMP) 2013-2020 and the Flemish Adaptation Plan (VAP) 2050
- Flemish Blue Deal
- River Basin Management Plans 2022-2027 for Scheldt and Maas
- Flemish Decree on Integrated Water Policy
- Regulation on infiltration of water
- Regulation concerning e.g., concentrate discharge to surface water: VLAREM II
- Permits for building and exploitation of combined infrastructure in the urban environment Omgevingsvergunningsdecreet (EMIS Navigator (vito.be)), milieulijk
- Water price structure is fixed by law and is the same for a) drinking water; b) sanitation; and c) wastewater treatment.
- Regulation for drinking water: Drinkwaterwetgeving (EMIS Navigator (vito.be))
- Permit requirement for groundwater use, which includes charges

Policies and regulation, Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Issues (-) and Strengths (+)

Source: Vlakwa

- (+) Incentive/penalty related to development of rainwater and Drought Plans
- (+) Regulations on the collection of rainwater in buildings
- (+) New Rainwater Regulation Decree
- (+) During periods of drought, the provincial governor can impose a temporary ban on the capture of water from surface water bodies
- (-) Lack of a legal framework for agriculture irrigation

Source: InAll, D5.3 (Gomes et al., 2022), Strategic Agendas (Schmuck et al., 2021; Glotzbach et al., 2023)

- (-) Missing National policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication
- (-) Missing National policies for stormwater management including its reuse
- (-) Improving permit issue process at national/local level
- (-) Lack of national/regional water reuse regulation
- (-) Missing national/regional guideline to clarify applicability of the regulation on water infiltration to water reused
- (-) Lack of National legislation for stormwater management including its reuse
- (-) Lack of a National/Regional regulatory framework that facilitates the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste
- (-) Lack of regulations about fertilizers and pesticide usage

Source: D5.5 (Schmidt et al., 2023)

- (+) Dashboards information-sharing platforms are in place
- (-) Need to improve transboundary coordination and the translation of EU legislation to the national and regional level
- (-) Need to align federal and regional risk assessment procedures. Disparities in risk assessment for water reuse as environment and water are regulated at the regional level, health is regulated at a federal level
- (-) Data on groundwater use in agriculture is likely to underrepresent actual use
- (-) Need to improve access to and coherence among different data platforms and stimulate cross-border data sharing
- (-) Need of a broader involvement of stakeholders in the value chain and in upstream and downstream areas could improve shared problem ownership and investment opportunities.
- (-) Lack of clarity and disparities between the regulation of rainwater, stormwater, and infiltration methods.

6 Analysis of major water-related issues

The major water-related issues identified in section 5.3 are herein analysed and presented, identifying the common issues among the LLs and the specific issues.

6.1 Common issues

6.1.1 Digitalisation and IoT on water

Most issues related to Digitalisation and IoT in water systems are shared among the LLs:

- National data protection laws derived from the GDPR, with consequences in data confidentiality and security, hinder data collection by the water utilities from smart meters of third parties (consumers)
- Lack of open data
- Low investment in data collection
- Low perception of the value of collecting and sharing data
- Need to identify the essential fit-for-purpose data

6.1.2 Drinking water supply

Regarding drinking water supply, the common issues fall under three dimensions, i.e. water efficiency, smart allocation, and extended quality for micropollutants and other contaminants of emerging concern:

- Need to improve water efficiency, as recently introduced by the new DWD, which establishes water leakage level should be assessed by all Member States and reduced if they are above a certain threshold. This requires planning and investment on the renewal of the supply network, and smart metering for water leakage and water consumption management, which requires to overcome the limitations related with the data confidentiality and security (see section 6.1.1).
- Need to allocate fit-for-purpose water quality, avoiding using drinking water for non-potable uses.
- Need to protect drinking water quality from micropollutants or unknown substances in the water sources, and to promote smart and cost-effective monitoring for these contaminants.

6.1.3 Energy

Regarding the energy, the common issues identified are:

- Need to promote energy efficiency in water systems and self-sufficiency in WWTPs, as considered in the recent EU policy development (Table 7) towards energy neutrality.
- Need to facilitate the management between the water systems and the energy distribution grid, in order to minimise the need for energy storage while ensuring the quality of electricity on the distribution grid.
- Lack of EU policy for climate efficiency in households, buildings, and neighbourhoods.

6.1.4 Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others

Concerning these resources recovery and beneficial use, the common issues identified are most related with biosolids/sludge and fertilizer nutrients, namely:

- Need for a consensual EU roadmap for biosolids/sludge management.
- Need to revise the EU directive concerning biosolids/sludge beneficial use in agriculture and the required characteristics/standards.
- Need for a consensual EU regulation concerning the organic fertilizers obtained from the urban wastewater treatment, including the required characteristics/standards, to promote their recovery and market acceptance.
- Need to look for value prepositive markets, such as urban landscaping; currently, the market for valuing nutrients is not appellative (low revenue).
- Need to shift the mindset and the semantics from “wastewater treatment” to “resource recovery”.
- Need to promote a generational change towards an increased market acceptance of recovered nutrients and biosolids (wording shift would help).

6.1.5 Water reuse

Regarding water reuse, a strong focus in five B-WaterSmart LLs, many common issues were identified:

- Lack of EU agenda and strategy on water reuse covering all uses, non-potable and potable, indirect (including managed aquifer recharge) and direct (going beyond the current regulation on minimum quality requirements for agriculture irrigation), to monitor and increase the safety of the current indirect reuse, and to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the water-energy-waste-food nexus.
- Lack of EU regulation and legislation for non-potable water reuse for urban (including irrigation and others) and industrial uses, and for potable uses, maintaining the fit-for-purpose principle and with clear instructions on the risk assessment process e.g., on how extensive the risk assessment for agricultural use should be.
- Lack of a uniform position across the EU countries regarding the accounting of indirect water reuse (some national statistics include, others do not).
- When WWTP discharges significantly impact the quality of a receiving water used for water abstraction (e.g., irrigation or industry), discharge and (indirect) reuse overlap. Therefore, either the water abstraction permit safeguards the treated wastewater quality (discharge permit), after dilution in the water body, fits the intended purpose, or the discharge permit safeguards the water quality for downstream indirect reuse. In both cases, the abstraction permit should secure the ecosystem maintenance flow. The cost coverage of the additional treatment (if needed) should reflect the best site-specific water resource management.
- Increased treated wastewater quality requirements for discharge to be introduced by the recast of the Urban Wastewater Directive can facilitate water reuse (lower or no additional/advanced treatment needed for reclamation).
- Monitoring is very relevant but often represents a big share of the direct costs of water reuse.
- Need of EU policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication to overcome the perception of worse water quality and high risk, among other (“yuck”) factors, to increase the water reuse acceptance.
- Business models, funding and pricing are critical factors.
- Multiple users improve technical (e.g., decrease peak demands) and economic feasibility of water reuse.
- The need to clarify if reclaimed water supply must be defined as an autonomous water service with a clear definition of responsibilities. Water reuse often requires a dedicated

treatment for reclamation and direct water reuse always requires a distribution network, the production and the distribution are not necessarily conducted by the same utility.

- The need of guidelines for the water reuse licensing process by the water authorities.

6.1.6 Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses

Regarding stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses, governance aspects include:

- adequate international agreements on transboundary water flow, particularly for the Southwest region, where surface water inflow is important;
- stakeholders' involvement in rain/stormwater management as a shared challenge with a clear definition of roles, responsibility and ownership, including who and how to pay for an unstable source as stormwater.

Major technical aspects identified are:

- the need to promote storage and use of rainwater/storm water in rural and urban (including households) spaces;
- the opportunity to use nature-based solutions to manage stormwater quantity and quality.

6.2 Specific issues

6.2.1 Digitalisation and IoT on water

In **Alicante, Spain**, technical and organizational security measures against unauthorized access were highlighted, as well as the lack of compliance control of the law and of clear guidelines on how personal data should be collected and processed in this specific context, and of updates addressing the current technological challenges and solutions.

In **Portugal**, the Portuguese Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority in the 4th Generation of the Quality of Service Assessment System, proposed the Security and Resilience Index, one for the water and another for the wastewater services, that addresses cybersecurity, together with other categories (water or wastewater safety, security (facilities, infrastructure and product), contingency to drought or floods, and emergency/crisis management). All categories cover different sub-classes within i) governance and operationalization, ii) risk management, iii) communication, and iv) planning (Cardoso et al., 2021, 2023). These indices were included in the WaterSmartness Assessment Framework (Silva et al., 2022).

6.2.2 Drinking water supply

Regarding drinking water supply, in **Norway**, the Norwegian Environment Agency monitors the SDGs and reports every 4 years to the UN Climate Convention.

6.2.3 Energy

Concerning energy, in **Spain**, even if several potential waste producers for biogas production exist, its use is limited by the waste transport cost and requirement of legal certification.

In **Norway** there is state financial support for establishing biogas production facilities but, due to its low populated areas, it was highlighted the need of scale optimization of these facilities, promoting

the already established intermunicipal collaboration. In addition, the consequences from the existing uncertainty concerning the organic fertilizer regulation were also identified.

In **Venice, Italy**, a not clearly defined National/Regional regulatory framework on the water-energy-waste nexus to promote circular economy, the complexity of the national regulatory system and the lack of regulation on energy recovery were identified.

6.2.4 Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others

In **Spain**, there are opportunities for nutrients recovery due to shortage of ammonia-based products, the rise of ammonia prices, and the existence of several potential consumers of the recovered product. However, the cost of the required equipment and product transport, and the penetration of these products in this competitive market are issues to overcome. In addition, the current regulatory framework exhibits inconsistency and heterogeneity, presenting a significant obstacle to achieving effective territorial governance in this domain. The great regulatory uncertainty and heterogeneity of criteria on sludge application generate a lack of confidence in the agents involved in the sector. This fragmented approach and absence of consensus further impede the formulation of a comprehensive plan for monitoring and evaluating sludge management practices. As a result, there are no proper assessment and monitoring mechanisms in place for the management of sludge. Moreover, it leads to a lack of funding for new investments and requires an update considering technological developments, international best practices, and environmental sustainability objectives.

In **Venice, Italy**, general roles are clear. However, the complexity of the national regulatory system and the unclear National/Regional regulatory framework on the water-energy-waste nexus, promoting circular economy, were again highlighted, as for the energy (section 6.2.3), as well as: not enough interlinkage between water and waste policies (e.g., “end of waste classification” delegated to the arbitrary “case by case” evaluation may impact N-salt valorisation); the need for a clear regulation concerning the N-recovery products; the need of a decision support system, shared knowledge and policy coordination at regional scale; scattered data to support the implementation and management.

6.2.5 Water reuse

In **Alicante, Spain**, whereas water reuse was signalled as **beneficial** to the implementation of other technologies, the underdevelopment of business models and the complexity in decision making (including the justification of the investment on water reuse to local administrations) were identified as **major issues**. Additionally, the value chain of reclaimed water and roles and responsibilities are not well defined, and there is an overlap and sometimes lack of involvement of the parties. Furthermore, there is a lack of policy coherence regarding the water allocated by a concession or a legitimate title for the private use of water, as it is sometimes not used by its holder, and rigidity in administrative concessions can create challenges for certain users, especially in situations where adjustments or adaptations are required due to changes in hydrological conditions or specific user needs.

In **LL East Frisia, Germany**, the topic of industrial water reuse is still new. A **national water strategy** has been finalized and adopted in 2023, in which water reuse was identified as a good option for protecting resources. Water reuse was also included in the amendment to the Drinking Water Ordinance. The microbiological stability of the water is an important factor for approval. The water must not only comply with the Drinking Water Ordinance at the time of sampling, but also

demonstrate a good prognosis for a very low microbial regrowth potential. Assessment and approval are carried out by the responsible regional authority. For **LL East Frisia** the responsibility for water reuse in dairy industry is spread across different authorities, which complicates decision-making. At federal level, one needs (i) a decision support and guidelines for authorities to approve water reuse for dairy industry solutions, (ii) to strengthen coordinated technical advice, (iii) bundled responsibility for industrial water supply in a central point of contact as Federal Office / Authority or others similar, (iv) political empowerment of health authorities to also consider the contribution of reuse approaches to overarching environmental policy objectives in the approval process. In addition, there is **a need** to politically uptake the technical input provided by water associations and to define required water for intended use, focusing on water quality instead of ‘history’. Furthermore, there is **a need** for more investment support for refinancing of high opex and capex.

In **Flanders, Belgium**, there is the **need** (i) to improve transboundary coordination and the translation of EU legislation to the national and regional level; (ii) to align federal and regional risk assessment procedures, to overcome disparities as environment and water are regulated at the regional level, whereas health is regulated at a federal level, (iii) to improve access to and coherence among different data platforms and stimulate cross-border data sharing, (iv) to promote a broader involvement of stakeholders in the value chain and in upstream and downstream areas to improve shared problem ownership and investment opportunities – return on investment for water-related innovations is low, causing heavy reliance on public funding. A **positive aspect** is the dashboards information-sharing platforms in place.

In **Lisbon, Portugal**, the national legal framework clarifies reclaimed water production as a new activity committed to multi-municipal wastewater systems and covers all non-potable uses (agricultural but also urban and industrial) though environmental uses were recently (2023) excluded. It does not allow selling/transferring reclaimed water to third parties (no secondary users allowed), which would increase water reuse potential and viability. ERSAR recommendation for water reuse financing is based on the “user pays” principle, meaning the additional treatment for reuse should be paid by the water user and not charged to the wastewater service. New national legislation will be needed after the new UWWTD is issued, which is an opportunity for a better coherence between urban wastewater treatment and water reuse policy and regulation. There is the need for planning and acting at local and river basin levels, e.g., drought and water scarcity issues should be dealt in advance by incorporating the principles and good practices in non-potable water uses in the city, evolving from the current situation to avoid the use of drinking water. Strategic planning, essential for successful water reuse, exists in Lisbon, also with the contribution from the B-WaterSmart project, evidencing the political awareness and willingness to reuse water. The national strategy and the regulatory environment for the water services are also favourable. On the one hand, the national strategic plan for 2030 addresses water circularity. On the other hand, the Portuguese (waste)water utilities must have in place strategic plans and ERSAR’s quality of service assessment (Cardoso et al., 2021) includes a reclaimed water production indicator with reference values depending on local water scarcity. The reclaimed water storage is also a success factor and, although the national legislation does not consider water reuse for aquifer recharge, the 2024’ State budget includes funding for a pilot project on managed aquifer recharge for a sound assessment of the environmental impact of this potential complementary solution for tackling water scarcity. It is important to integrate water reuse in local/regional water balance, and prioritise its uses, which should be decided according to the local environmental, technical, economic, and social circumstances. Regarding water resources management, in the scope of the ReWaterEU plan, the Portuguese government

proposes to implement measures for reducing water losses in distribution systems, optimising storage and transport infrastructures, reusing water for non-potable purposes in the urban, tourist, industrial and agricultural sectors, and investing in desalination plants. Outdated regulations on building water systems are a barrier to the licensing of rainwater harvesting and water reuse systems. Knowledge and information on reclaimed water quality evolution in the distribution network is lacking, as well as a service model defining who builds and operates this new network. In Lisbon, the legal framework is unclear regarding the existence of water supply utilities other than EPAL. Public awareness about the factors that may increase water scarcity in Lisbon, and nationwide, need to be promoted as well as collaboration among authorities, stakeholders, and potential users (urban, rural, or industrial), focusing on the benefits of using reclaimed water of fit-for-purpose quality.

In **Venice, Italy**, a national water reuse strategy and a clear national/regional regulatory framework facilitating circular economy across the nexus water-energy-waste are lacking. The national regulatory system complexity, ambiguities on roles/responsibilities in agricultural water reuse chain, and lack of data to support water reuse implementation and management are other issues identified.

6.2.6 Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses

In **Flanders, Belgium**, the Flemish Government recently approved the regional Rainwater Ordinance, incentives/penalties related to the development of Rainwater and Drought Plans (e.g., during drought periods, the provincial governor can impose a temporary ban on the capture of water from surface water bodies) exist, as well as regulations on use of the different water sources for irrigation and on rainwater harvesting in buildings. Nevertheless, several **major issues** are missing: a legal framework for agriculture irrigation, regulations about fertilizers and pesticide usage, and national policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication to improve shared problem ownership, environmental practices and investment opportunities; clarity between the regulation of rainwater, stormwater, and infiltration methods and national/regional guideline to clarify applicability of the regulation on water infiltration to water reused; national policies for stormwater harvesting and use, and improved permit issue process at national/local level; national/regional regulatory framework that facilitates the development of the circular paradigm across the nexus water-energy-waste; improved transboundary coordination and the transposition of EU legislation to the national and regional level; aligned federal and regional risk assessment procedures (e.g., environment risk assessment for water reuse is regulated at the regional level, whereas health risk assessment is regulated at a federal level). Dashboards information-sharing platforms are in place but the access to and coherence among different data platforms must be improved to stimulate cross-border data sharing, and data on groundwater use in agriculture is likely underestimated.

7 Recommendations

Based on the analysis of the major water-related issues (chapter 6), cross-cutting and water-related resource-specific recommendations were developed to policy makers at (i) European level, i.e., EU Commission, (ii) National/Regional level, i.e., Government, Water Resources and Water Services regulators/authorities, and (iii) local level, i.e., Municipalities, local authorities/agencies. The different degree of detail reflects each topics' relevance across the six LLs (cf. chapter 3 with the corresponding tools and technologies developed in B-WaterSmart to facilitate the uptake of water-smart solutions). The tools, particularly the #34-Water-smartness assessment framework and tool (a web tool assessing how 'water-smart' a system is), support the implementation of the recommendations proposed.

7.1 Cross-cutting recommendations

To support the development and implementation of water-related policies and regulations, cross-cutting recommendations include:

- Ensure coherence among sectors (water, energy, waste, food, health) and across levels (EU, national, local). For example, (i) exclude biosolids/sludge from waste legislation; (ii) the targets for renewable energy production and for water-related circularities need to be coherent, namely, the hydrogen production may aggravate the local water scarcity, compromising (agricultural and industrial) food production; (iii) the energy distribution grid management must consider the water utilities as energy consumers but also as producers.
- Promote a problem-driven research and innovation environment, e.g. water-oriented LLs.
- Promote stakeholders' engagement and co-work (e.g. following up B-WaterSmart Communities of Practice (CoPs) and the Innovation Alliance (InAll)), data-based decision-making, strategic planning, and resource allocation.
- Develop coherent EU-national-local strategic plans on water and related resources, supported by a clear, quantitative, and objective-driven assessment, e.g., the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework ([D6.3](#)), identifying the strategies/actions and estimating the human, financial and technological resources needed to reach the targets on the short, medium, and long-term.
- Create incentives to train and capacitate human resources regarding the adequate knowledge and competences to implement the strategic plans.
- Promote the SDGs' monitoring and international benchmark.
- Implement the assessment of the impact of performance-based access to funds for green-field investment and renewal.
- Create/empower to create/empower national, regional, and local water governance boards to enhance water governance and facilitate inclusive decision-making processes. These boards can contribute to more sustainable and effective water governance by overseeing water management policies, ensuring transparency, and facilitating inclusive decision-making. They would consist of representatives from government and regulation agencies, the water sector (public and private), water users, civil society, and academia.
- Promote collaborative work of competent authorities and water managers to continuously review and update regulations, for achieving the EU water-related objectives and taking into account technological advancements, international best practices, and environmental sustainability goals. For instance, the establishment of Water-Oriented Living Labs (WoLLs) creates very effective environments, particularly in highly regulated contexts, such as the

water sector, for collaborative innovation among public authorities water companies, technological and solution providers, and research institutes, facilitating the testing and improvement of P&R instruments (as demonstrated in LLs Lisbon and Venice).

- Engage the scientific community and other experts of the sector in decision-making processes to integrate their knowledge in robust and innovative governance.
- Promote public-private collaboration and facilitate information exchange among water management entities through discussion forums and benchmarking initiatives.
- Promote the mindset and semantics' shifting from "wastewater treatment" to "resource recovery" and valuing the water quality rather than its 'history', i.e., privileging 'water' over 'wastewater'. Adopt this new terminology in future EU documents and communication actions, and update the current ones accordingly.
- Promote a generational change towards an increased market acceptance of recovered water, nutrients and biosolids (wording shift would help).

7.2 Digitalisation and IoT on water

European level

- Promote mechanisms for the continuous update and monitoring of IT threats and solutions to ensure updated technical and organizational security measures against unauthorized access. These mechanisms often rely on sound performance assessment practices. An example is the use of the Security and Resilience Index for the water and for the wastewater services included in the WaterSmartness Assessment Framework (Silva et al., 2022). These indices address cybersecurity (as well as safety, security (facilities, infrastructure, and product), contingency to drought or floods, and emergency/crisis management), and cover governance & operationalization, risk management, communication, and planning (Cardoso et al., 2021, 2023).
- Produce guidelines or standards of fit-for-purpose data specification, comprehensively demonstrating the value of the shared data, both from the economic and the innovation points of view and addressing the integration of multiple systems and data sources.
- Clarify the boundaries between confidential and open data, promoting the safe availability of sound anonymous shared data.

National, regional, and local level

- Transpose the above to national and/or regional levels, when and if applicable.

7.3 Drinking water supply

European level

- Regulate or provide incentives for the development of strategic asset management of water supply systems for the prioritization of most cost-effective investments on the long term, towards network renewal and smart monitoring, assessing the progress through quantity and quality indicators.
- Minimise the discharge of microcontaminants in the water sources, by promoting point source control (e.g. of X-ray contrast media, cytostatics, cancer treatments and some antibiotics, in medical facilities) and considering that an improvement will be expected after the new UWWTD (COM(2022)541) enters into force, as it includes improved control.

- Promote research on simpler and cost-effective monitoring of proxy indicators of contaminants of emerging concern of costly and difficult analysis, e.g. pharmaceuticals.
- Monitor and regulate, particularly in water-scarce regions, the non-potable uses of drinking water, e.g., via licencing restrictions of water meters for irrigation or implementing strategic targets. For example, the Lisbon LL, the water-smartness strategic plan developed using the developed Water Smartness Assessment Framework ([D6.3](#)) establishes mid-term and long-term targets for eliminating the drinking water use in non-potable municipal uses by considering alternative sources mostly water reuse.

National, regional, and local level

- Transpose the above to national and/or regional levels, when and if applicable.

7.4 Energy

European level

- Promote and provide the means for energy efficiency in water systems and self-sufficiency in WWTPs towards energy neutrality, as considered in the recent EU policy development (new UWWTD), as addressed in LLs Alicante and Venice via biogas production for energy self-sufficiency.
- Facilitate the management, regarding production and use of energy by water utilities, between the water systems and the energy distribution grid (e.g., provide guidance/make mandatory the energy contracts to safeguard both the uptake and the upload of energy by the water utility), in order to minimise the need for energy storage while ensuring the quality of electricity on the distribution grid.
- Provide incentives for the adoption of water-energy efficiency certificates for housing (similar to the existing energy efficiency certificates, e.g. in the Lisbon LL).

National, regional, and local level

- Transpose the above to national and/or regional levels, when and if applicable.
- Better harmonise the water, energy, and waste policies, e.g.
 - assessing the impact of energy production from hydrogen on water resources and facilitate the co-digestion of waste for improved biogas production;
 - clarify the legal restrictions for sludge agricultural application, considering the contaminants involved, as this affects this use of sludge vs. energy production.

7.5 Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others

European level

- Co-produce an EU roadmap for biosolids/sludge management; consider net societal benefits in the decision making on management options, accounting for aspects such as the bioavailability of nutrients (e.g., phosphorus) and the energy content.
- Ensure coherence of policy and targets between biosolids recovery and biogas production.
- Revise the Council Directive 86/278/EEC concerning biosolids/sludge beneficial use in agriculture and the required characteristics/standards, defining a clearer allocation of responsibility along the biosolids value chain, involving the water utilities, the authorities and local actors in the development of circular solutions. Moreover, the inclusion in this legislation of clear requirements regarding the recovery of materials from biosolids/sludge is

a way to overcome the existing barriers to circular economy, in contrast to a sludge management guided by legislation on waste.

- Coherently, in the above revision, exclude biosolids/sludge from waste legislation to overcome the existing barriers to circular economy (no uniform rules across the EU), to improve predictability for investments for water utilities, and enhance confidence for the end-users.
- Deliver a comprehensive EU regulation concerning the organic fertilizers obtained from the urban wastewater treatment, including the required characteristics/standards, to promote their recovery and market acceptance, alongside with a clearer allocation of responsibility along the nutrients value chain, correcting the barrier created by the exclusion of sewage sludge of the scope of the Fertilisers Regulation (2019/1009/EU).
- Promote monitoring of phosphorus (P) as a critical raw material in Europe focusing on quality of materials with recovered phosphorus (e.g. biosolids and sludge); accordingly update regulations by adjusting the targets of P recovery from urban wastewater via biosolids land application at agronomic rate, irrigation with reclaimed water, fertilisers (Silva et al., 2016), considering also its beneficial use through the irrigation with reclaimed water as suggested in water reuse topic (e.g. via Regulation (EU) 2020/741).
- Promote research and the use of technologies that recover nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) from wastewater and sludge streams in a concentrated form (e.g., the inorganic precipitate struvite), increasing the options for reuse with reduced pathogen risk and improved ease of transportation. Regulation, such as the new UWWTD, can act as enabler for sludge treatment technology to evolve.
- Promote research on the impacts on soil, vegetation, animals, and humans resulting from the use of biosolids/sludge in agriculture.

National, regional, and local level

- Integrate local specificities in the nutrient and biosolids management systems: different solutions for different contexts.
- Prioritise the adaptation of existing sludge infrastructures for co-digestion, rather than solely focus on funding new infrastructures, to optimise resources and maximise the benefits of existing facilities.
- Establish a "Sludge Round Table" at the regional or national level to ensure effective monitoring and evaluation of sludge management practices, bringing together various stakeholders, including government authorities, companies, scientific and expert communities, and users. This initiative can help update regulations and address legal concerns within the sector.

7.6 Water reuse

European level

- A future revision of the Regulation (EU) 2020/741 should (i) extend its scope to urban, industrial, and environmental uses, establishing minimum requirements for other uses than agricultural irrigation, namely industrial and urban uses, maintaining the fit-for-purpose principle used for agriculture uses, (ii) reflect in the monitoring the knowledge about the system and its reliability, i.e., a higher effort during the validation period and then a decrease upon data records of water quality reliability, including simpler and cost-effective, ideally on-

line, monitoring of proxy/screening indicators of water quality, and (iii) account for the beneficial use or recovery of phosphorus through the irrigation with reclaimed water.

- Mandate the integration of water reuse into EU water resources management strategies and water resilience strategies (as foreseen in the new UWWTD).
- Develop an EU strategic agenda on water reuse covering all uses (non-potable and potable), indirect (including managed aquifer recharge) and direct (going beyond the current regulation on minimum quality requirements for agriculture irrigation), to monitor and increase the safety of the current indirect reuse, and to facilitate the development of the circular paradigm across the water-energy-waste-food nexus.
- Encourage the member-states to define priorities for reclaimed water uses, which should be decided according to the local environmental, technical, economic, and social circumstances. Reclaimed water should be clearly integrated in local/regional water balance (no investment in reuse if supply continuity is not secure).
- Agree on a uniform position across the EU countries on if and how to account for indirect water reuse – clarifying the boundaries between treated wastewater discharge and (indirect) water reuse, which impact the permits and the treatment required; the cost coverage of the additional treatment (if needed) should reflect the best site-specific water resource management; the environmental uses should be accounted for as direct or indirect water reuse, as well as managed aquifer recharge.
- Regarding managed aquifer recharge, clear instructions should be delivered for a sound assessment of its environmental impact and for risk assessment and management.
- Promote research and provide guidance on how to upgrade the current urban WWTPs to cope with the new requirements of the UWWTD recast and enable water reuse (e.g., to address both quaternary treatment and disinfection).
- Promote EU policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication to overcome the often-biased perception of worse water quality and high risk, among other (“yuck”) factors, to increase the water reuse acceptance – water quality should matter not its source, providing risk management is ensured.
- Develop guidelines for a Europe-wide coherent water reuse licensing (e.g., how far should the risk assessment go) and water reuse service provision (dedicated treatment, storage, and conveyance) and pricing.
- Promote research & innovation and subsequently develop policy and regulation on water reuse business models, funding mechanisms, and pricing, valuing opportunity costs and considering multiple users to improve economic (as well as technical, e.g., decrease peak demands) feasibility of water reuse.
- Promote research and pilot demonstration projects of direct potable reuse to develop sound guidelines of water quality and treatment process operation and redundancy needed to anticipate a solution for aggravated water scarcity, localised needs, emergency situations, as well as to build the trust of the society in water reuse safety (as addressed in Lisbon LL for food industry/beverage, in East Frisia LL in the dairy industry, and in Flanders LL for drinking water supply).

National, regional, and local level

In the **Alicante LL, Spain**, it is important to establish clear roles and responsibilities to promote the efficient use of reclaimed water. This can be achieved by defining common protocols that prevent entities from relying solely on their own discretion to promote reclaimed water, ensuring a more coordinated and efficient approach to the management of these resources. However, to ensure policy coherence at both regional and national levels, it is crucial to develop a more unified and consistent approach, that prioritises the long-term sustainability of resources and emphasises the

promotion and support for the expansion of reclaimed water. By aligning policies and strategies, a comprehensive framework can be created that effectively addresses the needs of all stakeholders involved. One of the key barriers in managing water resources is finding a balance between different water users, rural and urban areas, and future generations. To tackle this issue, it is necessary to change perceptions and increase flexibility in administrative water concessions. This can be achieved by implementing certain limits and supervision to ensure the responsible and efficient exchange of water resources. With proper oversight, it can prevent the misuse of water and ensure that it is utilised in a sustainable manner.

Regarding **East Frisia LL, Germany**, the following should be promoted at federal level: (i) a decision support and guidelines for authorities to approve water reuse for dairy industry solutions, (ii) to strengthen coordinated technical advice, (iii) bundled responsibility for industrial water supply in a central point of contact as Federal Office / Authority or others similar, (iv) political empowerment of health authorities to also consider the contribution of reuse approaches to overarching environmental policy objectives in the approval process. In addition, there is a need to politically uptake the technical input provided by water associations and to define required water for intended use, focusing on water quality instead of 'history'. Furthermore, there is a need for more investment support for refinancing of high opex and capex.

In **Flanders LL, Belgium**, the following recommendations should be addressed (i) to improve transboundary coordination and the translation of EU legislation to the national and regional level; (ii) to align federal and regional risk assessment procedures, as environment and water are regulated at the regional level, whereas health is regulated at a federal level, (iii) to improve access to and coherence among different data platforms and stimulate cross-border data sharing, (iv) to promote a broader involvement of stakeholders in the value chain and in upstream and downstream areas to improve shared problem ownership and investment opportunities (return on investment for water-related innovations is low, causing heavy reliance on public funding).

In **Portugal (Lisbon LL)**, all the recommendations at EU level apply. Regarding the specific context, current legislation does not allow a licensed reclaimed water user to pass on the reclaimed water to third parties due to risk management concerns. This is a major barrier to the implementation of water reuse in urban areas. The creation and regulation/licensing of a reclaimed water supply service could overcome this bottleneck through a producer- distributor-user(s) model, each party with an adequate risk management. Multiple users likely offer a steadier consumption with the inherent technical and financial advantages resulting from a decreased variation in demand throughout the year and among years, by a wider and more diverse number of interested parties.

The 'cost-recovery principle' established at EU level and the 'user pays' principle recommended in Portugal may impair the affordability/willingness-to-pay for water reuse vs. freshwater abstraction, unless water scarcity is reflected on the freshwater costs and/or the wastewater treatment for discharge, supported by the respective tariff, gets closer to the water reclamation requirements, as expected through the UWWTD recast. Water reuse often secures freshwater availability for other purposes, including drinking water production, agriculture irrigation, so the financial model should assess a fair share of water reuse costs, particularly investment, across water services and freshwater abstraction.

Strategic planning for water reuse, integrated in a broader regional water balance, is essential and should involve all key stakeholders and economic activities, and consider all existing sources,

including reclaimed water. Facilitating factors include the B-Water Smart Assessment Framework and the regulatory context, which requires the utilities to have in place strategic plans.

In **Venice LL, Italy**, it should be developed: (i) a national water reuse strategy and national/regional strategic plans, (ii) national/regional regulatory framework facilitating circular economy across the nexus water-energy-waste, (iii) national/regional regulation and legislation on industrial water reuse including specific substances, (iv) national policies for public engagement, awareness, and communication, (v) clarification of roles/responsibilities in agricultural water reuse chain, (vi) data to support water reuse implementation and management are other issues identified.

7.7 Stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses

European, national, regional, and local level

Regarding stormwater for agricultural irrigation and other uses (as addressed in Flanders LL), recommendations cover governance and technical aspects, namely:

- provide adequate international agreements on transboundary water flow, particularly in EU regions where surface water inflow is important;
- promote stakeholders' involvement in rain/stormwater management as a shared challenge with a clear definition of roles, responsibility, and ownership, including who and how to pay for an unstable source as stormwater;
- promote storage and use of rainwater/stormwater in rural and urban (including households) spaces; promote the use nature-based solutions to manage stormwater quantity and quality;
- promote smart monitoring and control of the water quality for the safety of the fit-for-purpose stormwater use with the appropriate treatment.

7.8 Next step - policy briefs development

Additional discussions need to be carried out for the topics selection to better reflect the B-WaterSmart efforts and results, and to also address the developments relevant to this subject from other projects of the CIRSEAU cluster (of five sister H2020 projects (on the topic “Building a water-smart economy and society”).

Even though, in order to contribute to the definition of the topics for the policy briefs to be developed, based on the current recommendations, as described in section 4.3, each participant of the Policy and Regulation interactive session individually ranked the six topics discussed, according to their relevance for the B-WaterSmart policy briefs, and the same ranking was carried out by each LL. The results correspond to the following ranking (more details presented in Annex 2):

- Water reuse (1st rank individually and per LL)
- Drinking water supply (2nd rank individually and per LL)
- Stormwater (3rd rank individually, 4th rank per LL)
- Digitalization and IoT on water (4th rank individually, 6th rank per LL)
- Energy (5th rank individually and per LL)

- Recovery of nutrients, biosolids and others (6th rank individually and 3rd per LL)

The ranking is not coincident and may be biased by the different number of participants per table, which reflects the direct interest of the participants (section 4.3.2). This reinforced the need for further discussions, after which the following set of policy briefs was agreed (available in [D5.8](#)):

- Policy brief #1. *Unleashing the untapped energy potential of wastewater - Recommendations for achieving the energy neutrality targets of the revised EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive.*
- Policy brief #2. *Accelerating water smartness by successfully implementing the EU Water Reuse Regulation.*
- Policy brief #3. *Applying Urban Wastewater and Sludge as Nutrients for Agriculture Use - Recommendations for EU Policy Reforms.*
- Policy brief #4. *Fostering circular water infrastructure - Boosting a circular water economy by creating an enabling environment for large-scale systems and infrastructure to support the development of alternative resources.*

8 References

Aleksić, N.; Šušteršič, V.. Future of water recycling – A review of the direct potable water reuse. *Recycling and Sustainable Development* 15, 2022, doi: 10.5937/ror2201029A

Ashley, R.; Gersonius, B.; Horton, B. Managing flooding: from a problem to an opportunity. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, 2020, 378: 20190214. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0214>.

Baptista, J.M. 2018. Lessons learned from water reform in Portugal. LIS-Water. Lisbon International Centre for Water. <http://www.ppa.pt/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/5.-LIS-Water-20180723.pdf>

Barrero et al. (2021) Manual of Data Specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs (Deliverable 4.1 of B-WaterSmart project). Publicly available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5da52e955&appId=PPGMS>

Beard, J.E.; Bierkens, M.F.; Bartholomeus, R.P. Following the Water: Characterising de facto Wastewater Reuse in Agriculture in the Netherlands. *Sustainability* 2019, 11(5936), doi: 10.3390/su11215936

Bertrand-krajewski, J.-L. Integrated urban stormwater management: Evolution and multidisciplinary perspective. *Journal of Hydro-environment Research*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jher.2020.11.003>.

Bichai, F.; Ashbolt, N. Public health and water quality management in low-exposure stormwater schemes: a critical re-view of regulatory frameworks and path forward. *Sustainable cities and society*, 2017, Vol. 28, pp.453-465, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2016.09.003>

Bocken, N.; Boons, F.; Baldassarre, B. Sustainable business model experimentation by understanding ecologies of business models. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2019, 208, 1498-1512, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.10.159.

Cardoso, M.A.; Rosa, M.J; Brito, R.S.; Silva, C.; Beceiro, P.; Jorge, C.; Alegre, H.; Martinho, G.; Pina, J.; Silveira, A.; Alves, V.; Ana, J.B.; Ramos, M.; Carrega, M. Guide for assessment of the quality of water and waste services provided to users 4th generation assessment system. Technical Guide 27. 2021, ISBN 978-989-8360-44-1. (Updated version, in Portuguese, [Guia Técnico 27 v2024.pdf](#)).

Cardoso, M.A., et al. Recommendations for refinement of the water-smartness framework and its transformation into a dashboard-type software. H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D1.3. 2022

Cardoso, M.A.; Brito, R.S.; Silva, C.; Rodrigues, S.; Rodrigues, R.; Costa, A.; Cardoso, J.; Jorge, C.; Alegre, H.; Rosa, M.J. Quality of Urban Water Services Provided to Users: Assessment System and the Portuguese Path through Four Generations, Lessons Learned and New Challenges. *Sustainability* 2023, 15, 15273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115273>

Conrad, A.; Müller, A.; Das, B.; Schieren, J.; Lukas, B.; Brauner, R. Set of policy briefs on regulation and policy instruments. H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D5.8. 2024. <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/set-of-policy-briefs-on-regulation-and-policy-instruments-d5-8/#>

EC, 2000. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. Official Journal of the European Union L 327. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/60/oj>

EC, 2006a. Directive 2006/12/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2006 on waste. Official Journal of the European Union L 114. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32006L0012>

EC, 2006b. Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 February 2006 concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC. Official Journal of the European Union L 64. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2006/7/oj>

EC, 2006c. Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration. Official Journal of the European Union L 372. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2006/118/oj>

EC. 2008a. Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. Official Journal of the European Union L 348. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/105/oj>

EC, 2008b. Council Directive 2008/114/EC of 8 December 2008 on the identification and designation of European critical infrastructures and the assessment of the need to improve their protection. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0114>

EC, 2015. Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. Better regulation for better results - an EU agenda. COM (2015)215 final. European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52015DC0215>

EC, 2020. Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe. Brussels. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

EC, 2021. European Research Executive Agency, Frijns, J., Charpentier, L., Malamis, S. et al., Water in the circular economy policy development – Workshop report with findings from demo cases of Horizon 2020 projects, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/092630>

EC, 2022. Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast). COM(2022)541 2022/0345 (COD). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/HIS/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0541>

EEA, 2017. European bathing water quality in 2016. EEA Report No 5/2017. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/european-bathing-water-quality-in-2016>.

EEA, 2017. Perspectives on transitions to sustainability. EEA Report No 25/2017. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/perspectives-on-transitions-to-sustainability>.

EEA, 2022. Circular Economy policy innovation and good practice in Member States. ETC CE working paper. European Environment Agency. https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/draft-report-for-dg-env_final.pdf

EEA, 2021. Water resources across Europe — confronting water stress: an updated assessment. EEA Report No 12/2021. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/water-resources-across-europe-confronting>

Eureau, 2021. 8 big challenges for the water sector in the next 10 years , European Federation of National Water Services Association. <http://www.eureau.org/topics/10-big-challenges>.

EEC, 1991a. The Council of the European Communities. 2014. Consolidated text: Council Directive of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste water treatment (91/271/EEC). Official Journal of the European Union L 271. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1991/271/2014-01-01>

EEC, 1991b. The Council of the European Communities. 2008. Consolidated text: Council Directive of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (91/676/EEC). Official Journal of the European Union L 375. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1991/676/2008-12-11>

Engel, A.; Leminen, S. & Aarikka-Stenroos, L. Urban Living Lab as a Circular Economy Ecosystem: Advancing Environmental Sustainability through Economic Value, Material, and Knowledge Flows, 2021, Sustainability, 13(5), 2811. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052811>

EU, 2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

EU, 2020a. Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse. Official Journal of the European Union L 177. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/741/oj>

EU, 2020b. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast). Official Journal of the European Union L 435. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2020/2184/oj>

EU, 2022a. Directive (EU) 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/EC. <https://www.europeansources.info/record/proposal-for-a-directive-on-the-resilience-of-critical-entities/>.

EU, 2022b. European Parliament, Council of the European Union. Decision (EU) 2022/591 of the of 6 April 2022 on a General Union Environment Action Programme to 2030. Official Journal of the European Union L 114/22.

Filho, W. L., Özuyar, P., Dinis, M. a. P., Azul, A. M., Alvarez, M. G., Da Silva Neiva, S., Salvia, A. L., Borsari, B., Danila, A., & Vasconcelos, C. R. F. Living labs in the context of the UN sustainable development goals: state of the art. 2022, *Sustainability Science*, 18(3), 1163–1179.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01240-w>

Flores et al. (2024) Guidelines of circular economy models for each Living Lab (Deliverable 4.3 of B-WaterSmart project).

Frijns, J.; Smith, H.M.; Brouwer, S.; Garnett, K.; Elelman, R.; Jeffrey, P. How Governance Regimes Shape the Implementation of Water Reuse Schemes. *Water* 2016, 8(12), doi: 10.3390/w8120605

Geissdoerfer, M.; Savaget, P.; Bocken, N.M.P. & Hultink, E. The Circular Economy – A new sustainability paradigm?. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2017. 143. 757–768.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.048>

Geissdoerfer, M.; Pieroni, M.; Pigosso, D., & Soufani, K. Circular business models: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2020, 277, 123741. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.12374

Gomes et al. (2022) Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions across 6 Cases - Policy and Governance (Deliverable 5.3 of B-WaterSmart project). Publicly available at <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/drivers-and-barriers-for-water-smart-solutions-across-6-cases-policy-and-governance-d5-3/>

Glotzbach et al. (2023). Final version of strategic agendas agreed by CoPs. Milestone 22 B-WaterSmart.

Graham, A. Sustainable drainage systems: delivering multiple benefits for people and wildlife. In S. M. Charlesworth & C. A. Booth (Eds.), *Sustainable surface water management - A handbook for SuDS*, 2016, 91–104. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

<http://doi.org/10.1002/9781118897690.ch7>.

Hirano M.; Latorre C. Guidelines for Public Participation in the Regulation of Urban Water Services. International Water Association, 2020.

IDN. Contributos para uma Estratégia Nacional de Ciberdefesa. Projeto de investigação. Instituto da Defesa Nacional. Contributions for a CyberSecurity National Strategy. Research Project. National Defense Institute, 2017. (In Portuguese)

Inagro. 2023. Moet ik een vergunning hebben om open put water te gebruiken? Accessed 07/02/2023. <https://inagro.be/themas/water/waterbronnen/open-put-water/vergunning>

IRAR. Planos de segurança da água para consumo humano em sistemas públicos de abastecimento. Guia técnico 7. Instituto Regulador de Águas e Resíduos (IRAR) /UMinho. Water safety plans for human consumption in drinking water systems. Technical guide 7. Water and Waste Regulation Institute/UMinho. IRAR, 2005 (173 p). (In Portuguese)

ISO. International Organization for Standardization. ISO 55000:2014. Asset management Overview, principles and terminology. Geneve, Switzerland, 2014.

IWA. Water Utilities Pathways in a circular economy. International Water Association, 2016.

Jaramillo, M.F.; Restrepo, I. Wastewater Reuse in Agriculture: A Review about its Limitations and Benefits. *Sustainability* 2017, 9(1734), doi: 10.3390/su9101734

Kapetas, L.; Fenner, R. Integrating blue-green and grey infrastructure through an adaptation pathways approach to sur-face water flooding. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, 2020, 378: 20190204. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0204>.

Lei n.º 58/2019, de 8 de agosto. Lei de Proteção de dados. *Diário da República* n.º 151/2019, Série I de 2019-08-08.

Lima, S.; Brochado, A.; Marques, R.C. Public-private partnerships in the water sector: A review. *Utilities Policy* 2021, 29, 101182 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2021.101182>.

Mukherjee, M.; Jensen, O. Making water reuse safe: A comparative analysis of the development of regulation and technology uptake in the US and Australia. *Safety Science* 2020, 121, 5-14.

Nielsen, C. How Regulation Affects Business Model Innovation, *Journal of Business Models* 2023, Vol. 11, No. 3, pp. 105-116

OECD. Principles on Water Governance. OECD Water Governance Programme, 2015. <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/regionaldevelopment/OECD-Principles-on-Water-Governance-en.pdf>

OECD. Recommendation of the Council for Agile Regulatory Governance to Harness Innovation, 2021a. <https://www.oecd.org/mcm/Recommendation-for-Agile-Regulatory-Governance-to-Harness-Innovation.pdf>

OECD. Managing Environmental and Energy Transitions for Regions and Cities, 2020. OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/f0c6621f-en>.

OECD. Regulatory Policy Outlook 2021, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/38b0fdb1-en>.

OECD. Better regulation for the green transition, OECD Public Governance Policy Papers 2023, No. 40, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/c91a04bc-en>

Oghazi, P. & Rana, M. Circular Business Model Challenges and Lessons Learned—An Industrial Perspective, 2018, *Sustainability* 10, no. 3: 739. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10030739>

PENSAARP 2030. Plano Estratégico para o Abastecimento de Água e Gestão de Águas Residuais e Pluviais 2021–2030. <https://apambiente.pt/agua/PENSAARP2030>

Pérez et al. (2024) Guidelines to improve new Business Models at Living Labs (Deliverable 4.4 of B-WaterSmart project).

Pescod, M.B. Wastewater treatment and use in agriculture: FAO irrigation and drainage paper 47, 1992, Rome: FAO. <https://www.fao.org/3/t0551e/t0551e00.htm>

Popp, D. Induced innovation and energy prices. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 2022, 92(1), 160–180. doi: [10.1257/000282802760015658](https://doi.org/10.1257/000282802760015658) (*op. cit.* in Ren and Albrecht (2023))

Rebelo et al. (2021). CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab, D1.1 B-WaterSmart. Available online: <https://b-watersmart.eu/local-communities-of-practice-in-six-living-labs/>

Ren, Q.; Albrecht, J. Toward circular economy: The impact of policy instruments on circular economy innovation for European small medium enterprises. *Ecological Economics* 2023, 207 (2023) 107761 doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107761

Riazi, F.; Fidélis, T.; Matos, M.V.; Sousa, M.C.; Teles, F.; Roebeling, P. Institutional arrangements for water reuse: assessing challenges for the transition to water circularity. *Water Policy* 2023, Vol 25 No 3, 218 doi: 10.2166/wp.2023.155

Rosa, M.J; Silva, C; Rodrigues, R.; Catarino, A.R.; Rodrigues, S.; Eiró, V.; Alegre, H.; Cardoso, M.A. (2025). Regulation of urban water services in Portugal. Alignment between the quality-of-service assessment system and recent developments in the legal framework. *Pi 2025 - 10th IWA Conference Benchmarking, Performance Assessment and Regulation of Water Services, Poland.*

Salminen, J.; Määttä, K.; Haimi, H.; Maidell, M.; Karjalainen, A.; Noro, K.; Koskiahho, J.; Tikkanen, S.; Pohjola, J. Water-smart circular economy – Conceptualisation, transitional policy instruments and stakeholder perception. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2022, 334 (2022) 130065 doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.130065
SERV. 2022. Advies hemelwaterverordening. Accessed 07/02/2023. <https://www.serv.be/serv/publicatie/advies-hemelwaterverordening>

Schmuck et al. (2021). First draft of the LL strategic agendas and feedback for WP2-5 and WP7. Milestone 12 B-WaterSmart.

Silva et al. (2023). Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework. D6.3 B-WaterSmart. Publicly available at <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/final-version-of-the-water-smartness-assessment-framework-pdf-deliverable-6-3/>

Schmidt et al. (2023). Drivers and Barriers proposal for a new governance model (Deliverable 5.5 of B-WaterSmart project). Publicly available at <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/drivers-and-barriers-proposal-for-a-new-governance-model-d5-5/>

Syke, 2021. [https://www.syke.fi/en-US/Research_Development/Circular_economy/Water_in_circular_economy\(45493\)](https://www.syke.fi/en-US/Research_Development/Circular_economy/Water_in_circular_economy(45493)).

Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij. N.d.(a). Vergunning nodig voor onttrekken van oppervlaktewater? Accessed 07/02/2023. <https://www.vmm.be/water/kwaliteit-waterlopen/blauwalgen/faq-blauwalgen/vergunning-nodig-voor-de-captatie-van-oppervlaktewater>

Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij. N.d.(b)). Vlaamse Hydrografische Atlas. 07/02/2023. <https://www.vmm.be/data/vlaamse-hydrografische-atlas>

Vlaamse Regering. N.d. (a). Verplichte installatie van een regenwaterput en infiltratiesysteem bij nieuwbouw en herbouw. Accessed 07/02/2023. <https://www.vlaanderen.be/verplichte-installatie-van-een-regenwaterput-en-infiltratiesysteem-bij-nieuwbouw-en-herbouw>

Vlaamse Regering. N.d. (b). Melding en vergunning voor gebruik van grondwater. Accessed 07/02/2023. <https://www.vlaanderen.be/melding-en-vergunning-voor-gebruik-van-grondwater>

Vlaamse Regering. 1995. Vlarem II: Besluit van de Vlaamse regering van 1 juni 1995 houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake milieuhygiëne.
<https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=19128&woLang=nl>

Vlaamse Regering. 2022. Besluit van de Vlaamse Regering tot vaststelling van een gewestelijke stedenbouwkundige verordening inzake hemelwater en tot opheffing van het besluit van de Vlaamse Regering van 5 juli 2013 houdende vaststelling van een gewestelijke stedenbouwkundige verordening inzake hemelwaterputten, infiltratievoorzieningen, buffervoorzieningen en gescheiden lozing van afvalwater en hemelwater.
<https://beslissingenvlaamseregering.vlaanderen.be/document-view/62CFB28A8E6C4430A8898A15>.

WAREG. Water Regulatory Governance across Europe. Report 1. European Association of Public Authorities with supervisory and tariff-setting powers on the drinking water and wastewater sectors, 2021

Zammar, J.; Scholefield. Rain city strategy: making green rainwater infrastructure mainstream in Vancouver. In Proceedings of LESAM/PI 2019, 2021, Vancouver, Canada, 23-27 September.

Zhou, Q. A Review of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems Considering the Climate Change and Urbanization Impacts. *Water*, 2014, 6(4), 976–992. <http://doi.org/10.3390/w6040976>.

9 Online references

EC-SP, 2023. European Commission. About the European Commission. What the European Commission does in strategy and policy. https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/what-european-commission-does/strategy-and-policy_en (Accessed 14/12/2023).

EC-ECCE, 2023. European Commission, Energy, Climate change, Environment. Topic Water. EU efforts on the global water agenda – Beyond UN 2023 Water Conference. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/eu-efforts-global-water-agenda-beyond-un-2023-water-conference_en (Accessed 14/12/2023).

EC-Water, 2023. European Commission, Energy, Climate change, Environment. Topic Water. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water_en (Accessed 14/12/2023).

EU news, 2024 (Euractiv.com). Portugal says EU needs plan to promote water availability to fight scarcity, <https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/news/portugal-says-eu-needs-plan-to-promote-water-availability-to-fight-scarcity/> (Accessed 25/01/2024).

Kallai, T., SA Silva, N., & Klaus, W. (2020). Report on the development of innovative models. LIVERUR. Retrieved 2023, from <http://www.liverur.eu/>

RWO, 2023. De gewestelijke hemelwaterverordening 2023, <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl/verordeningen/de-gewestelijke-hemelwaterverordening-2023> (Accessed 12/02/2024).

WAREG (2023). The essence of the Water Framework Directive, <https://www.wareg.org/articles/the-essence-of-the-water-framework-directive/> (Accessed 4/01/2024).

WISE (2023). WISE-Freshwater. Policy and Reporting, <https://water.europa.eu/freshwater/policy-and-reporting> (Accessed 4/01/2024).

World Bank, 2020. om Waste to Resource: Shifting Paradigms for Smarter Wastewater Interventions in Latin America and the Caribbean, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/water/publication/wastewater-initiative>. (Accessed 14/12/2023).

Annex 1 | List of B-WaterSmart tools and technologies

B-WaterSmart tools and technologies

#	Name of tool / technology
1	Water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry: piloting of Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF) effluent post-treatment for using in artisanal beer production
2	Aquifer storage recovery: suitability of aquifer storage recovery for strategic storage of drinking water.
3	Effluent reuse for drinking water production: technologies to upgrade secondary effluent for input into the drinking water cycle.
4	Compact combinatory treatment technologies for industrial water reuse: Pilot combination of technologies
5	Urban stormwater reuse for agriculture: Demonstration of treatment technologies.
6	Combined treatment of vapour condensate & milk/whey permeate for reuse in dairy industry: Demonstration of treatment combination to assess quantity and quality of reuse water, residuals, operational costs and monitoring.
7	Nitrate-selective electrodialysis reversal (EDR): Piloting of novel membrane for nutrients separation from brines and use in fertigation.
8	Brine Electro-chlorination: Piloting of technology for on-site production of sodium hypochlorite.
9	Ammonia evaporation CEVAP: Piloting of a novel low thermal evaporation technology (CEVAP) for ammonia recovery from co-anaerobic digested sludge.
10	Oil and fat co-digestion technology: Pilot scale validation of the valorisation of oil and fats
11	Ammonia recovery from concentrated WWTP streams: Stripping/absorption pilot system.
12	Efficient small-scale biogas production at small wastewater treatment plants: Clustering of plants, combi solutions with several material flows
13	Microturbines for energy recovery: Demonstration of energy recovery from WWTP effluents.
14	IoT sensors for infiltration detection: Registration of inflow to wastewater networks and testing of sensor combination.
15	Smart water meters for leak detection: Piloting of online capabilities to sample pressure, flow, temperature, and acoustic data from household smart meters
16	Water Reuse Strategic Platform: Comprehensive, transferable, interoperable evaluation system for Water Reuse based on FIWARE based Internet of Everything platform.
17	Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action
18	RE-ACTOR: Smart water allocation & negotiation tool for water reuse
19	Sludge Management Platform: Comprehensive, transferable, interoperable evaluation system for Sludge Management based on FIWARE Internet of Everything platform.

20	UWC Observatory: Urban Water Cycle Observatory: Open data information for public and reserved data sets to input into decision-making tools.
21	Stormwater Reuse Management System: Operational management of a stormwater buffer basin and the connected sub-irrigation system
22	UWOT: model for simulation of the urban water cycle from source-to-treatment-to-tap, supporting planning and assessment of distributed interventions.
23	Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool: Tool for GIS-based analysis of optimal demand-resource patterns (using FREEWAT)
24	Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network
25	Water-energy-P balance planning module
26	QMRA+: Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment for water reuse and agriculture
27	RA-Reuse: Risk Assessment (RA) for Urban Water Reuse module
28	Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool: Automatized day-to-day water demand forecasting
29	iWidget+ Platform (or Fiware enabled multi-dashboard): Online platform for water information at utility and customers premises
30	iWidget+ Platform (or Fiware enabled multi-dashboard): Online platform about I/I for wastewater networks
31	ASR-pro tool: predicting water quality after subsurface storage
32	Digital Enabler: Integrated digital support system to enable Resource Recovery (RR) and Circular Economy (CE) at regional scale
33	Climate-readiness Certification tool: Toolkit for 'Water Smart for Climate-Ready' Building Certificates
34	Water-smartness assessment framework and tool: a web tool assessing how 'water-smart' a system is.

Annex 2 | Interactive session on policy and regulation

Discussions outcomes

a. Digitalisation and IoT | Table 1

Table 1 counted with sixteen participants and discussed the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations on policy and regulation regarding **Digitalisation and IoT**. The output is presented in Figure 6 and Table 11.

Figure 6. Digitalisation and IoT | Working table 1.

Table 11. Working table 1 outcome | Digitalisation and IoT

Working table 1 - Digitalisation and IoT			
Issue	P&R Recommendation	Scale EU, National (N), Regional (R), Local (L)	Dimension Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)

1. Lack of open data 2. Lack of investment in the institutions (cost of collecting data)	- Improve the knowledge of the data standard FIWARE	-	-
	- to get data from companies you have to make it worth for them	- EU, N	- E
	- marketing advantage (would facilitate getting access to some type of data)	-	-
	- Funding: make eligibility depend on the projects complying with data standards	- EU	- E
3. Data confidentiality 4. Low perception of the value of collecting and sharing data •	- Incentives: “connecting Europe facility” equivalent for smart water systems	-	-
	- incentives with sings attached		-
	- Differentiation: for governmental data for enforcement versus company data for decision support	- N	-
	- Confidentiality		
• What data and what metrics are essential to the policy and regulation objectives? • Do we have a data strategy with data for which purpose	- Pose and hopefully answer the question	-	-
	- What is different for after “post BWSM”	-	-
	- Data the strategy exists at the “high” level but needs to be defined for each type of data and purpose	- N - R	-
	- the BWS project is in a good position to make recommendations on		

	what data and metrics are key for policy and regulation		
	- link to EU open data spaces initiative		
	- who needs to be involved (at what stage)		

b. Drinking water | Table 2

Table 2 counted with fifteen participants and discussed the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations on policy and regulation regarding **Drinking water**. The output is presented in Figure 7 and Table 12. Working table 2 outcome | Drinking water. In blue text are identified the LL three major issues.

Figure 7. Drinking water | Working table 2

Table 12. Working table 2 outcome | Drinking water

Working table 2 – Drinking water			
Issue	P&R Recommendation	Scale	Dimension
1. Protecting drinking water quality: which micropollutants or unknown	- guidance on safe practices enabling reuse of water while adequately protecting the quality of	- EU, N EU, National (N), Regional (R), Local (L)	Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)
			- P, En, T, L

<p>substances could be in reclaimed water?</p> <p>- No groundwater recharge in drinking water protection areas</p> <p>- first use of the water sources like rain or drainage water?</p>	resources (e.g., groundwater)		
	- enhance the role of drinking water supply company regional groundwater management and stakeholder engagement	-	- En, S
<p>2. ensuring drinking water quality at point of consumption (network monitoring) incentives for safe fast meters in pipelines</p>	- clear technical guidelines for monitoring drinking water network	- EU, N	- T, L
	- public information about drinking water quality easily available: more tests? marking of consumption points?	- EU - N	-L - S
<p>3. definition in regulations:</p> <p>- where do you need drinking water and where could it also be water (reclaimed water) that fulfils certain quality aspects</p> <p>- fit for purpose</p>	- clear technical guidelines national for using alternative water sources	- N	- T, L
	- to decrease pressure on drinking water, prioritize the use of reclaimed water in sectorial areas such as agriculture industry	- E, N	- P
<p>- more easy introduction of new technologies (lightening the GDPR rules)</p> <p>- leakages in distribution</p> <p>- effective production of drinking water from sea water Use</p>	- implementation of drinking water regulation enabling substitution of drinking water by reclaimed/reuse of water		
	- safety related with the decrease of raw		

<p>Reverse Osmosis, lower costs less use of energy</p> <p>- lack of investments to renew drinking water supply network which leads to a massive waste of potable water and of course, to a lot of energy waste (indirect)</p>	water quality and quantity		
	- leakage pressure demands management		
	- integrated and quick response monitoring for integrated water plans		- L
	- reliable long term drinking water supply (CC): decentralize, multiple sources, (indirect) use, concentrate disposal, health issues (risk assessment methodologies)		
	- help all water providers prepare for the coming climate change challenges through a framework for preparing		
	- country “relevant” purposeful legislation, e.g., the water directive being “irrelevant”/ making management unnecessary in one country than in another		

c. Nutrients, biosolids and others | Table 4

Table 4 counted with eight participants and discussed the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations on policy and regulation regarding **Nutrients, biosolids and others**. The output is presented in Figure 8 and Table 13. In blue text are identified the LL three major issues.

Figure 8. Nutrients, biosolids and others | Working table 4.

Table 13. Working table 4 outcome | Nutrients, biosolids and others

Working table 4 – Nutrients, biosolids and others			
Issue	P&R Recommendation	Scale	Dimension
1. Product / value issues - Dynamic discharge licensing for nutrients - Require strategic plans for nutrient	- Nutrients and sludge (biosolids) are different. Sludge needs to be clearly integrated in directive → treatment issues (note: UWWTD revision)	EU, National (N), Regional (R), Local (L)	Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)
		- EU	- P

<p>management across water / farming / land use, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulation policy: characteristics / standards of by-products are not defined 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product value: to look at recover and reclamation. Semantics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P 	
<p>2. Market / revenue issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market penetration - By-products market incentives. Agriculture - Scarce market acceptance of nutrients recovered from WWT - Taxing conventional fertilizers - Enabling legislation for nutrient recovery and reuse markets - Upcycling N, not only fertilizers, e.g. protein production for animal feed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value prepositive market - e.g., urban landscaping: (<i>for</i>) valuing nutrients (<i>but</i>) revenue is hard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build markets at national scale: necessary to move to decentralized - Digital tools (<i>note: for supporting these markets</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU
<p>3. Transaction / buyers and sellers' issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality standards - Knowledge: systematic treatments, standardize waste types - Sludge reuse in agriculture: lack of a coordinated EU directive - Arrangements for nutrients neutral developments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generational change → students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E, R, N, L 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - S 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wording → change semantics: not wastewater treatment, change to recover 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU, N 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P 	

<p>4. Non-specified issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Old infrastructure - Financing - Incentives - Develop/implement new technologies / more efficient (e.g., IEX, membranes) - Nitrogen and P recovery, not just removal 	<p>--</p>	<p>--</p>	<p>--</p>
---	-----------	-----------	-----------

d. Reclaimed water | Table 5

Table 4 counted with seventeen participants and discussed the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations on policy and regulation regarding **Reclaimed water**. The output is presented in the Figure 9 and Table 14. In blue text are identified the LL three major issues.

Figure 9. Reclaimed water | Working table 5.

Table 14. Working table 5 outcome | Reclaimed water

Working table 5 – Reclaimed water			
Issue	P&R Recommendation	Scale	Dimension
		EU, National (N), Regional (R), Local (L)	Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)
1. business and funding issues - no secondary users allowed - secondary uses, the possibility of a user to	- subsidy - incentives = money not spent or groundwater wells, other conventional sources	-N - R	- P, E
	- funding investment for companies to do	- EU	- E, S

<p>sell and bought reclaimed water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the responsibility to build and operate the reclaimed water network - CAPEX costs for infrastructure (storage, transport) - can it be financed by the drinking water tariff? - a new infrastructure needed, new costs - water reuse: need for regulation for other reuse, e.g. drinking water; Reg. 2020/741 requires rationale market development for users 	investment: water efficiency label		
	- reclaimed water funding scheme supported partially by drinking water tariff	- EU	- E
	- secondary users allowance	- N - EU	- L - P, E
<p>2. water quality issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - missing guidelines for the water authorities - perception of worse water quality for irrigation - unclear how extensive risk assessment for agricultural use should be - water quality, is legislation sufficient? - Licensing process 	- Improve control at source, e.g. anti-contrast effluent	- EU	- S,P, L, En
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - actual risks, a major definition: to align freshwater-reclaimed water-the actual agricultural source - avoid arbitrary precautionary approach 		
<p>3. indirect reuse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the indirect the best/self-intrusion 	- reports direct and indirect reuse independently	- EU	- P, L, Env

- for the direct costs and responsibility distribution	- we need a clear definition of what is meant with indirect reuse	- EU	- P, L, Env
--	---	------	-------------

e. Stormwater | Table 6

Table 6 counted with eleven participants and discussed the main needs and requirements to support the recommendations on policy and regulation regarding **Stormwater**. The output is presented in Figure 10 and Table 15. In blue text are identified the LL three major issues.

Figure 10. Stormwater | Working table 6.

Table 15. Working table 6 outcome | Stormwater

Working table 6 – Stormwater			
Issue	P&R Recommendation	Scale	Dimension
		EU, National (N), Regional (R), Local (L)	Political (P), Economic (E), Social (S), Technological (T), Legal (L), Environmental (Env)
Synthesis LLs 3 Major issues: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unstable source of water: how to cope with costs, who pays per unstable source 2. stop drainage, start to store and reuse rainwater/storm 			

<p>water is business case</p> <p>3. stakeholder involvement: heavy rain/stormwater management as a shared challenge</p>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - legal aspects: responsibility (municipality, land owner, plant owner) and governance - ownership: investments versus operational costs and revenues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure local adaptation and not strictly focus on the population equivalent or plant size 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P, E
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - incentives and codes for rainwater use in buildings, private properties 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of large scale and small scale infrastructure to retain water in the cities storage who is responsible for storage to reuse? - where to find place for storage: legal process for obtaining I - space conflicts little public space: need to cooperate to do measurements in private property - mandatory management in households and industrial parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stakeholders integrated management and planning integrating stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R, L 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - definition of stormwater “pure rain water” but polluted because of roads and roofs - quality differences - ecosystem aspects - increasing monitoring will increase costs - combined sewer systems: where you must have overflows due to quantity of stormwater rushing to the treatment plants - Lack of regulation on stormwater reuse at household level (especially its quality) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stormwater basins converted into nature-based solutions which treat and improve water quality, e.g., floating structures, wetlands... 		
--	---	--	--

Ranking of 6 topics | relevance to produce the B-WaterSmart policy briefs

Using the Mentimeter, each participant individually ranked the six topics (1. Digitalisation and IoT; 2. drinking water; 3. energy; 4. nutrients, biosolids and others; 5. reclaimed water; and 6. stormwater.), according with the relevance to produce the B-WaterSmart policy briefs. The same ranking was carried out by each LL. The results are presented in Figures 6 and 7, respectively.

Mentimeter

Rank the topics for the policy briefs (all):

Figure 11. Ranking of all participants

Mentimeter

Rank the topics for the policy briefs (LLs):

Figure 12. Ranking of LLs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.